

Trends and projections in the EU-ETS in 2025

The EU Emissions Trading System in numbers

Authors:

Christian Nissen, Johanna Cludius, Sabine Gores, Reena Skribbe,
Nora Wissner (Öko-Institut)

EEA project manager:

Melanie Sporer

Cover design: EEA

Cover image: Pixabay. Free for commercial use, no attribution required

Publication Date: December 2025

EEA activity: climate change mitigation and adaptation

Legal notice

Preparation of this report has been funded by the European Environment Agency as part of a grant with the European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation (ETC-CM) and expresses the views of the authors. The contents of this publication do not necessarily reflect the position or opinion of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union. Neither the European Environment Agency nor the European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation is liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of the information contained in this publication.

ETC CM coordinator: Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO)

ETC CM partners: AETHER Limited, Citepa, Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI), EMISIA, Stiftelsen NILU (NILU), Öko-Institut e.V. Institut für Angewandte Ökologie, Öko-Recherche GmbH - Büro für Umweltforschung und -beratung, Rijks Instituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM), Gauss International Consulting S.L., Transparency for life (T4L), Klarfakt e.U., Exergia S.A., Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML), Umweltbundesamt GmbH (UBA).

Copyright notice

© European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation, 2024

Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged. [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (International)]

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17967837 (from Zenodo)

More information on the European Union is available on the Internet (<http://europa.eu>).

European Topic Centre on

Climate change mitigation

<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cm>

etccm@vito.be

Contents

Contents	1
Summary.....	3
About this report	3
Main findings	3
1 Overall EU ETS1 Developments	5
1.1 Emission Trends in the EU ETS1	5
1.2 Development of CO ₂ Prices in the EU ETS1	6
1.3 Supply of allowances	8
1.3.1 Auctioned allowances and MSR intake	8
1.3.2 Free allocation	9
1.3.3 Supply and demand for allowances and impact on the allowance price.....	10
1.3.4 The Market Stability Reserve.....	11
1.4 Linking of the EU ETS1 with other emission trading systems.....	12
1.4.1 Swiss Linking.....	12
1.4.2 UK Linking.....	13
2 Sector-specific Analysis	14
2.1 Stationary Installations.....	15
2.1.1 Combustion	16
2.1.2 Industry.....	23
2.2 Transport under the EU ETS1	29
2.2.1 Aviation.....	30
2.2.2 Maritime	34
3 Projections and Policy Impacts.....	38
3.1 Stationary	38
3.1.1 Overview.....	38
3.1.2 Projection methodology and scenario updates	40
3.1.3 Emission trends by country	41
3.1.4 Emission trends by sector.....	43
3.2 Aviation.....	44
3.2.1 Overview.....	44
3.2.2 Emission trends	44
3.3 Maritime Transport	46
3.3.1 Overview.....	46
3.3.2 Emission trend.....	46
4 Focus Topic: EU ETS2.....	49

Overview.....	49
4.1 Emission trends	52
List of abbreviations	54
References.....	55
Annex 1.....	58

Summary

About this report

The annual 'Trends and projections in the EU ETS' report provides an overview of the development of the European Emissions Trading System (EU ETS1) since 2005 and up to 2024. It documents key trends in emissions, allowance prices, supply-demand dynamics, as well as sectoral developments and projections. An overview of the upcoming EU ETS2 system is also presented.

All historical ETS data used in this report are based on a snapshot from the Union Registry dated 04 November 2025. At this point in time, the data precede the full compliance cycle, which may lead to minor revisions in later releases. Based on EU Member States' emissions projections, it also gives an outlook on projected future developments until 2050. The geographical scope covers all EU ETS Member States, including the EU-27, as well as Iceland, Norway, and Liechtenstein. Although the United Kingdom (UK) has left the EU ETS1, electricity generators in Northern Ireland remain part of the system and are therefore included in this report.

Main findings

Total EU ETS1 emissions increased from 1,150 Mt CO₂-eq in 2023 to 1,185 Mt CO₂-eq in 2024. This rise is largely attributable to the inclusion of maritime transport in the scope of the EU ETS1 together with growth in emissions from air transport. For maritime transport, 89.9 Mt CO₂ were reported for the first time. Emissions from stationary installations declined significantly (-6 %), while aviation emissions grew (+15 %) as air traffic nearly approached pre-pandemic levels.

Allowance prices experienced a downward correction after the record high price levels of recent years. The average price of EU allowances (EUAs) stood at EUR 64.8/t CO₂-eq in 2024, compared with EUR 83.6/t CO₂-eq in 2023. Aviation allowances (EUAAAs) followed a similar trend. The decline reflects weaker economic conditions, the easing of natural gas prices and the continued expansion of renewable energy, while price signals continue to provide strong decarbonisation incentives.

The supply of allowances in the EU ETS1 increased in 2024 due to higher auction volumes following the inclusion of maritime transport. At the same time, free allocation to industrial installations decreased further to 500 million allowances (-7 % compared to 2023). For the first time, the revised ETS framework triggered the automatic cancellation of surplus allowances in the MSR above the 400 million threshold. The Market Stability Reserve (MSR) absorbed 271 million allowances and remained a key market balancing mechanism.

The sectoral analysis shows that emissions from power generation fell further due to declining fossil fuel use and the continued expansion of renewables, while industrial emissions remained broadly stable. Aviation increasingly relied on emission allowances from the stationary and maritime sectors as the emissions cap for aviation is significantly lower than emission from these sectors. The maritime transport sector entered the system and started with full auctioning, though only 40 % of emissions from this sector were subject to surrender obligations in 2024.

Projections submitted by Member States indicate a continued decline of stationary EU ETS1 emissions until 2030. Under the WEM scenario (with existing measures), reductions of about 61.7 % compared to 2005 are expected, while under the WAM scenario (with additional measures) reductions may reach up to 65.3 %. For the first time aviation emissions are projected to decrease from 2030, while maritime transport is expected to record a moderate decline in emissions. The EU ETS1 2030 target of a 62 % reduction therefore appears achievable.

The report also covers the introduction of EU ETS2 for buildings and road transport. This new system entered a transitional phase in 2024. A recent Council decision and European Parliamentary vote make it likely that the start of the system will be postponed to 2028. The EU ETS2 is based entirely on auctioning and will be complemented by the Social Climate Fund, which will become operational in 2026 and receive its first financing from EU ETS1 revenues in 2025.

Overall, the results confirm that the EU ETS remains a cornerstone of European climate policy. Its scope has been significantly expanded through the inclusion of additional sectors and the creation of EU ETS2. The projections indicate that the 2030 target is within reach, while further adjustments will be necessary to secure the trajectory towards climate neutrality by 2050.

1 Overall EU ETS1 Developments

Key messages:

- Total stationary verified EU ETS1 emissions declined strongly from nearly 2,093 Mt CO₂-eq in 2005 to around 1,033 Mt CO₂-eq in 2024 (-51%), with the long-term downward trend driven by climate policies, the growing share of renewable energy in power generation and the ongoing industrial decarbonization.
- The apparent increase in total verified EU ETS emissions between 2023 and 2024 (+3%) reflects the inclusion of maritime transport, which contributed 89.9 Mt CO₂ in its first year of coverage, rather than a reversal of the long-term decline.
- In 2024, the downward trend in emissions from stationary installations continues (-6%), albeit at a slower rate than in 2023, while aviation emissions continue to rise (+15%) as air traffic approached pre-pandemic levels.
- EUA prices reached historic highs in 2021-2023 before correcting to an annual average of EUR 64.8/t CO₂ in 2024. Despite the decline, price levels remain well above pre-2021 values and continue to provide strong decarbonisation incentives.
- Auction volumes rose to 497 million allowances in 2024, mainly due to the maritime extension, while free allocation fell to 500 million allowances (-7 % compared to 2023), continuing the long-term downward trend.
- The Market Stability Reserve (MSR) absorbed 271 million allowances in 2024. For the first time, the new cancellation rule reduced the MSR holdings to the legal maximum of 400 million allowances, resulting in the invalidation of 271 million units.

1.1 Emission Trends in the EU ETS1

Figure illustrates the development of verified emissions covered by the EU ETS1 from 2005 to 2024, disaggregated by stationary installations (including estimates for scope adjustments), aviation, maritime transport and emissions from the United Kingdom until 2020¹. Scope -adjustments are reflecting the expansion of the ETS scope over time for new countries, sectors and gases and ensuring comparability and consistency across the time-series².

During the first and second trading periods (2005-2012), emissions were dominated by stationary installations, with verified emissions of approximately 2,093 Mt CO₂-eq in the initial years. Aviation was included in the EU ETS1 in 2012, initially with a limited scope. From the third trading period onwards (2013–2020), aviation emissions became an established part of the EU ETS1, initially contributing modestly but increasing steadily over time. The fourth trading period (2021-2030) reflects significant changes, such as the inclusion of maritime transport (starting in 2024) and the withdrawal of the United Kingdom³ from the EU ETS1.

¹ An exception are electricity-generating installations in Northern Ireland that are still part of the ETS1.

² Scope-adjustment estimates (“estimate to reflect current scope”) are included to ensure comparability across trading periods

³ An exception are electricity-generating installations in Northern Ireland that are still part of the ETS1.

Overall, emissions from stationary installations exhibit a clear downward trend across all periods, reflecting the impact of enhanced climate policies, the transition to renewable energy sources and an ongoing decarbonisation in industry. The scope-adjusted estimates allow for a consistent comparison of historical emissions with the current coverage of the EU ETS1 in its fourth trading period.

Between 2023 and 2024, total verified emissions reported under the EU ETS1 increased from 1,150 Mt CO₂-eq to 1,185 Mt CO₂-eq. This apparent rise does not reflect a reversal of the long-term downward trend but is largely explained by the extension of the EU ETS1 scope to include maritime transport from 2024 onwards. Maritime activities added a substantial new source of emissions. In addition, aviation emissions rose slightly in 2024 as air traffic recovered to near pre-pandemic levels, while emissions from stationary installations continued their significant decline.

Figure 1-1 Verified Emissions: EU ETS1 (2005–2024)

Note: The estimate to reflect current scope takes into account emissions (not split by activity) for those countries, sectors and activities that have not been part of the EU ETS1 since its inception in order to provide a consistent time series. Emissions from the United Kingdom exclude electricity generators in Northern Ireland but include other ETS1 installations located there. Electricity generators from Northern Ireland are included under the 'Stationary' category.

Source: EEA (2025b)

1.2 Development of CO₂ Prices in the EU ETS1

During the first two trading periods (2005-2007 and 2008-2012), EU Allowances (EUA) prices were volatile and generally low. Phase 1 (2005-2007) saw prices rise above EUR 30/t CO₂ in 2006 but drop to near zero in 2007 due to oversupply and the fact that allowances could not be banked into Phase 2 and lost validity at the end of this first 'trial phase' in 2007. In Phase 2 (2008-2012), prices ranged between EUR 10 and EUR 20/t CO₂ before falling below EUR 7/t CO₂ by 2012 amid the global financial crisis and surplus allowances. In addition to the economic downturn, the extensive use of international Kyoto credits (CERs and ERUs) during Phase 2 increased the supply of units and further suppressed allowance prices (see EEA 2019, p. 23).

Figure 1-2 Development auf CO₂ Prices in the EU ETS1 (2005–2024)

Source: EEX (2025), ICE (2021)

Between 2013 and 2017, EUA prices remained at a relatively low level. The average price in 2013 was EUR 4.33/t CO₂-eq, increasing moderately to EUR 5.76/t CO₂-eq by 2017. This phase was characterised by a structural surplus of allowances resulting from the economic recession and the extensive use of international credits. The introduction of the Market Stability Reserve (MSR) in 2019 provided initial incentives to reduce the surplus.

From 2018 onwards, a significant upward trend in certificate prices has been observed. The average price reached EUR 15.50/t CO₂-eq in 2018 and climbed to EUR 24.72/t CO₂-eq in 2019. The peak level of EUR 29.46/t CO₂-eq in 2019 reflected the market’s reaction to the gradual reduction of supply through the MSR.

In 2021 and 2022, the market experienced strong price dynamics. In 2021, the average price doubled compared to the previous year, reaching EUR 54.15/t CO₂-eq. In 2022, an average price of EUR 80.18/t CO₂-eq and a maximum value of EUR 97.51/t CO₂-eq marked a historical high. This development is linked to the adoption of the EU Climate Law in 2021, setting legally binding targets for 2030 and 2050, as well as the “Fit for 55” package of policies and instruments aimed at reaching the 55 % emissions reduction target in 2030, which also increased ambition of the EU ETS. In addition, the tightening of natural gas supply from Russia led to a surge in gas prices and a temporary shift from gas to coal in power generation, contributing to higher ETS emissions and thus higher allowance price (see Nissen et al. 2023, p. 8).

In 2023, the average EUA price remained at a high level at EUR 83.60/t CO₂-eq. In 2024, a correction occurred, with the average price falling to EUR 64.76/t CO₂-eq. This development reflects dampened economic activity and the rising share of renewable energy in electricity generation. Despite the consolidation, the price level remains well above pre-2021 values and continues to provide a strong decarbonisation incentive.

The price trends for EU Aviation Allowances (EUAA) closely followed those of EUAs, which is to be expected given that both can be used interchangeably within the EU ETS1. In 2023, the EUAA average price peaked at EUR 82.33/t CO₂-eq before dropping to EUR 64.83/t CO₂-eq in 2024.

1.3 Supply of allowances

The supply of allowances in the EU ETS1 consists of two main components: the auctioning of allowances (Figure 1-3) and free allocation (Figure 1-4).

1.3.1 Auctioned allowances and MSR intake

The following graph illustrates EU ETS1 auctions for the stationary sector since 2013 (the start of the third trading period in the EU ETS1). In 2024, a total of about 600 million allowances were auctioned, including 219 million allowances where proceeds were allocated to various funds such as the Innovation Fund, Modernisation Fund, Recovery and Resilience Facility, and, from 2025 on, the Social Climate Fund. The increase in auctions in relation to these funds led to an increase in the overall auction volumes in 2025 compared to previous years.

Figure 1-3 EUA auction quantities and MSR intake (2013-2025)

Note: * planned auctions in 2025
MSR intake that has actually taken place in the respective calendar years
Auctioned amounts according to the Auctioning Calendar and TNAC publication

Source: EC (2025b), EEX (2025), ICE (2021)

The number of allowances auctioned each year is influenced by the Market Stability Reserve (MSR), which adjusts the auction volumes based on the Total Number of Allowances in Circulation (TNAC). The TNAC reflects the balance of supply and demand in the EU ETS1 since the begin of the second trading period in 2008. Since its introduction in 2019, the MSR has withheld allowances from auction each year due to the

TNAC exceeding the upper threshold of 833 million EUA and thus being above the maximum allowable surplus level of EUAs. In 2024, the MSR intake equalled 271 million allowances, reflecting a declining trend in withheld volumes since 2019.

The quantities auctioned for EU-level funds have further increased in recent years, as shown in Table 1-1. In 2024, the total volume of allowances auctioned for the Innovation Fund, Modernisation Fund and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) reached 219 million, representing a doubling compared to 2021. This increase is primarily driven by auctions for the RRF, which brought forward volumes that were initially scheduled for the second half of the trading period 2021–2030. The revenues support investments in the green transition and the phase-out of Russian fossil fuels under the REPowerEU initiative.⁴ From 2025 onwards, additional auction volumes will be allocated to the newly established Social Climate Fund, which aims to support vulnerable households and transport users during the transition to climate neutrality and in light of the incoming EU ETS2 (cf. Section 4).

Although the Social Climate Fund is linked to the introduction of EU ETS2 for buildings and road transport, the fund is partly financed with EU ETS1 allowances, serving as an early financing mechanism ahead of the new system’s full implementation.

Table 1-1 Auctions for funds in million emission units (2020-2025)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Modernisation Fund	-	69	68	67	97	88
Innovation fund	50	40	40	21	35	35
Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)	-	-	-	35	87	87
Social Climate Fund	-	-	-	-	-	50
Total	50	109	108	123	219	260

Source: EEX (2025)

1.3.2 Free allocation

In the EU ETS1, the majority of allowances are auctioned. Electricity generation generally does not receive free allocation, whereas industrial sectors may receive free allowances based on historical activity levels and product-specific benchmarks. Sectors at risk of carbon leakage are eligible for 100% of the benchmark-based allocation, while others receive a declining share over time. In addition, the conditionality provisions under the revised EU ETS Directive will increasingly link free allocation to decarbonisation efforts by industrial installations. From 2026 onwards, a further reduction in free allocation is expected due to the application of updated benchmark values.

Free allocation volumes have declined substantially since 2013 (Figure 1-4). Between 2013 and 2020, the annual amount of free allowances allocated to existing installations decreased steadily from 873 million to 674 million. In 2024, a total of 500 million allowances were allocated for free, representing a 7% decrease compared to 2023 and continuing the gradual downward trend. These free allocations accounted for approximately 42% of the total verified emissions in 2024.

⁴ For further information on the use of EU ETS auctioning revenues, see: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/use-of-auctioning-revenues-generated>

Figure 1-4 Free allocation of EUAs (2013-2024)

Source: EEA (2025b)

To ensure equal treatment of new and existing installations, the New Entrants’ Reserve (NER) continues to provide free allowances during the fourth trading period. The NER consists of 200 million allowances drawn from the Market Stability Reserve (MSR) and unused Phase 3 allocation. However, no stationary installations have received NER allowances since 2021.

Under Article 10c of the EU ETS Directive, a derogation from the general rule of no free allocation to electricity production was used in Phase 3 by eligible Member States to support the modernisation of their power sectors. During Phase 4, up to 40% of a country's auction volume may be used for this purpose. Of the ten eligible countries, only Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania have decided to make use of the Article 10c derogation in Phase 4, while the others have opted to transfer the allowances either to the Modernisation Fund or to regular auctioning. However, although these countries apply the derogation, no free allocations under Article 10c have been issued so far in Phase 4, as the required national implementation frameworks are still pending.

1.3.3 Supply and demand for allowances and impact on the allowance price

Figure 1-5 illustrates the annual balance between the supply of and demand for allowances in the EU ETS 1. In 2024, stationary verified emissions declined further to approximately 1,030 Mt CO₂-eq. At the same time, the total supply of allowances (comprising free allocation and auctions) amounted to 997 million allowances. As in the previous years, demand continued to exceed supply, leading to a further reduction of the market surplus.

The continued decline in emissions was mainly driven by reduced fossil fuel use in the power sector and starting decarbonisation in energy-intensive industries (see section 2.1). On the supply side, auction

volumes increased compared to 2023, due in part to the inclusion of maritime transport into the EU ETS1 and the continued auctioning of allowances for EU-level funds, including the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

The Market Stability Reserve (MSR) continues to play a central role in balancing the market by reducing auction volumes based on the Total Number of Allowances in Circulation (TNAC). Whether the declining surplus will result in a lower MSR intake in the future will depend on the evolution of emissions and the volume of allowances in circulation.

Figure 1-5 EUA auction quantities (2005-2025)

Note: Auctioned amounts include primary market sales by Member States in the second trading period. Graph does include UK until 2020
 *Auctions: to be auctioned in 2025

Source: EEA (2025b)

1.3.4 The Market Stability Reserve

Figure 1-6 shows the development of key Market Stability Reserve (MSR) indicators since its operational start in 2018. The MSR intake is determined annually based on the Total Number of Allowances in Circulation (TNAC), as published by the European Commission (EC 2025b).

At the end of 2024, the TNAC amounted to 1.15 billion allowances. As this value remains well above the upper threshold of 833 million allowances, the MSR will absorb 24 % of this surplus. This corresponds to 276 million allowances that will be withheld from auctions between September 2025 and August 2026.

At the End of year 2024 the MSR contained 671 million allowances. At the beginning of each year the total number of allowances held in the MSR is reduced to the maximum of 400 million allowances. At the beginning of year 2025 this resulted into the automatic invalidation of 271 million allowances, as the

volume held in the reserve at the end of year 2024 exceeded the ceiling introduced in the revised ETS Directive. The MSR ceiling was introduced in the revised EU ETS Directive and aims to limit the accumulation of allowances.

These developments underline the MSR’s strengthened role in stabilising the EU ETS1. As long as the TNAC remains above the threshold, significant auction volume reductions will continue. The regular invalidation mechanism further ensures that the market surplus does not rebuild over time.

Figure 1-6 Key MSR indicators and values (2018-2025)

Note: Number of allowances in the MSR at the end of the year, except for 2025, where values are given for the beginning of the year. TNAC for 2025 is not yet available and will be published 1 June 2026.

Source : EC (2025b) and previous TNAC publications

1.4 Linking of the EU ETS1 with other emission trading systems

Linking the EU Emissions Trading System 1 (EU ETS1) with other emissions trading systems entails the mutual recognition of allowances under defined conditions. The objective is to enhance cost efficiency through an expanded market and more harmonised carbon pricing. A linking agreement with the Swiss Emissions Trading System (Swiss ETS) has been in place since 2020. In addition, options for a future linkage with the United Kingdom Emissions Trading Scheme are currently under consideration.

1.4.1 Swiss Linking

Since 1 January 2020, the EU ETS1 has been linked to the Swiss ETS. This entails the mutual recognition of allowances: Swiss allowances (CHUs) can be used for compliance in the EU ETS1, and vice versa. While the systems are technically connected via their respective registries, the overall volume of Swiss allowances remains limited, and the quantitative impact of the linking on the EU ETS1 is correspondingly minor.

The aviation sector is fully integrated into the linking arrangement. Emissions from flights from the European Economic Area (EEA) to Switzerland fall under the EU ETS1, while flights from Switzerland to the EEA are covered by the Swiss ETS. Aircraft operators benefit from a "one-stop shop" approach, whereby only one competent authority, either in an EEA Member State or in Switzerland, handles compliance matters, and only a single operator holding account is required.

In 2024, aircraft operators administered by EEA countries received approximately 0.33 million Swiss allowances free of charge and reported 0.68 million tonnes of CO₂-equivalent emissions for operations covered by the Swiss ETS. Conversely, operators administered by Switzerland reported 1.06 million tonnes of emissions for flights covered under the EU ETS1 and received around 0.28 million free EU aviation allowances (EUAs).

1.4.2 UK Linking

Since Brexit, the United Kingdom has operated its own Emissions Trading Scheme (UK ETS), which replaced the UK's participation in the EU ETS1 as of 1 January 2021. The UK ETS was deliberately designed to mimic key structural elements of the EU system, including the sectoral scope, the cap-and-trade approach, MRV rules and auction mechanisms. However, it differs in several respects. For instance, the annual emissions cap started approximately five percentage points lower than the UK's allocation under the EU ETS1 and is set to decline more rapidly in line with the UK's net-zero 2050 target. The UK ETS also incorporates a reserve price and a cost-containment mechanism (CCM), while the EU ETS1 applies a quantity-based supply adjustment via the Market Stability Reserve (see ICAP 2025b).

On 19 May 2025, the UK and the EU reached a formal agreement to work toward linking the UK ETS with the EU ETS1. This was laid out in a Common Understanding under the Trade and Cooperation Agreement. The agreement outlines the objective of enabling mutual recognition of allowances and exempting bilateral trade from the respective Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanisms (CBAMs) (ICAP 2025a).

Despite the political agreement, no concrete implementation timeline has been established. The technical requirements for linkage are significant, including alignment of cap trajectories, auction design, allocation rules, and market stability provisions. Observers estimate that linkage is unlikely to occur before 2028, with some assessments pointing to 2029 or 2030 as more realistic (Twidale and Abnett 2025).

Nonetheless, governments and market participants emphasize the potential benefits. A linked system would facilitate price convergence, reduce compliance costs, improve market liquidity, and help avoid CBAM-related costs for cross-border trade. For UK industry, estimates suggest potential annual savings of up to £800 million once the EU CBAM enters into force in 2026 (Bonnet 2025).

According to a recent UK government modelling study, linking the UK ETS with the EU ETS1 could result in a long-term GDP gain of approximately 0.1 % by 2035 compared to a non-linked scenario (see UK Government 2025).

2 Sector-specific Analysis

Key messages:

Stationary installations:

Emissions continued the downward trend of recent years with -6 % in 2024 compared to 2023, reaching 1,033 Mt CO₂-eq. This is a considerable reduction, but nevertheless slowdown compared to the sharp decline of 17% between 2022 and 2023.

Combustion sector:

Since 2005, combustion emissions from stationary installations declined by more than a half (-53%). Reductions continued with 9 % between 2023 and 2024 and were driven by coal and gas phase-down and higher renewable and nuclear generation. Lignite and hard coal power plants accounted for the largest reductions (-17 Mt and -32 Mt CO₂ respectively).

Five countries (Germany, Poland, Czechia, Italy, Spain) contributed almost 75 % of total power plant emissions. Power sector emissions fell in nearly all major emitting Member States, with particularly strong reductions in Portugal (-42 %) and France (-33 %).

Industrial sector:

Industrial emissions remained largely stable (-0.5 %), reflecting limited structural transformation despite short-term output reductions.

From 2021-2024, reductions were driven mainly by high gas prices that unlocked efficiency gains and led to reduced production, not by breakthrough decarbonisation.

Cement and lime, iron and steel, and refineries accounted for nearly three-quarters of industrial EU ETS1 emissions in 2024.

Free allocation continues to shield most industrial emissions, with 98.6 % of cement and lime emissions covered in 2024.

From 2026, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) will gradually replace free allocation, for imports of cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertiliser, and hydrogen sector, phasing in fully by 2034.

Aviation:

Emissions rose by 15 % in 2024 to 64 Mt CO₂, reflecting continued post-pandemic recovery.

The supply-demand gap was -45 Mt EUAAs in 2024.

The sector is increasingly reliant on purchasing EUAAs from the stationary and maritime sectors.

Maritime transport:

Maritime transport is included in the EU ETS1 for the first time in 2024, with verified emissions of 89.9 Mt CO₂.

Shipping companies must surrender allowances for 40 % of their verified emissions in 2024, rising to 100 % by 2026.

Emissions are concentrated in a few countries, with Greece, Italy and Spain each reporting more than 10 Mt CO₂.

This chapter provides a sector-specific analysis of developments under the EU ETS1 for the period 2005 to 2024. It covers stationary installations (combustion and industrial activities) and transport under the EU ETS1 (aviation and maritime). The objective is to provide a more detailed understanding of trends observed across these sectors.

2.1 Stationary Installations

In 2024, the verified emissions from stationary installations in the EU ETS1 amounted to a total of 1,033.3 Mt of CO₂-eq. This corresponds to a decrease of 6% compared to the previous year. Emissions from combustion (activity code 20) fell by 9 % to 588.9 Mt, while industrial emissions (activity codes 21-99) only recorded a slight decrease of 1 % to 444.4 Mt (see Table 2-1Table 2-).

The total quantity of emission allowances (EUAs) made available amounted to 985.8 million in 2024. Of this, 487.8 million EUAs (45%) were allocated for free to existing installations and 592.8 million EUAs (55%) were auctioned. Compared to 2023, this represents decreases of 2% and increase of 15% respectively. No allocation was reported for new installations or capacity expansions in this reporting year. The balance between the demand for and the supply of allowances amounted to -42.6 million EUAs, compared to -82.4 million EUAs in the previous year.

In the same period, 271 million EUAs were withdrawn via the Market Stability Reserve (MSR) - a decrease of 16 % compared to 2023. The average EUA market price fell to €64.76/t CO₂ (2023: €83.60/t; see Table 2-).

Table 2-1 EUA demand, supply and price (stationary installations), 2023-2024

	2023	2024	Change 2023-2024
Verified emissions (Mt CO₂-eq.)	1096.8	1123.2	+2%
Combustion emissions	649.9	588.9	-9%
Industrial emissions	446.8	444.4	-1%
Maritime emissions*		89.9	
Total supply of allowances (millions of EUA)	1,014.4	1080.6	+7%
Free allocation (incumbents, new entrants)	496.8	487.8	-2%
To existing installations	496.8	487.8	-2%
To new entrants and capacity extensions	-	-	
Auctioned amounts	517.6	592.8	+15%
Supply/demand balance (millions of EUA)	-82.4	-42.6	
MSR intake (millions of EUA)	-323	-271	-16%
Average EUA price (EUR)	83.60	64.76	-23%

Note: Although maritime transport is not part of the stationary sectors, verified emissions from maritime activities are included in this table to reflect the full EUA demand under the EU ETS1. The inclusion is necessary to ensure consistency with the logic of the supply-demand balance, which considers total demand for general EUAs regardless of sector. Shipping companies use EUAs to cover their obligations as there are no sector-specific allowances for maritime transport.

Source: EEA (2025b)

The development since 2005 is shown in Figure 2-1. Emissions from fuel combustion activities, (activity code 20) fell from 1,254 Mt in 2005 to 589 Mt in 2024 (-53 %). The decline was particularly pronounced in the years from 2019 onwards. Emissions from industrial plants have remained more constant. Overall, they fell from 523 to 444 Mt of CO₂-eq (-15 %) since 2005.

The decline in emissions from combustion is mainly driven by changes in the fuel mix and political measures for decarbonisation, particularly in the power sector. Although electricity consumption has

recently increased, the emission intensity of power generation continues to decrease due to the growing share of renewables and the phase-out of fossil fuels. The relatively stable industrial emissions indicate a less advanced transformation process in this segment (see section 2.1.2).

Figure 2-1 Verified Emissions: Stationary installations (2005–2024)

Note: Values exclude the United Kingdom (for all years) and do not include scope estimates.

Source: EEA (2025b)

2.1.1 Combustion

Combustion installations (activity code 20) constitute the largest category of stationary installations within the EU ETS1 and are responsible for 50% emissions recorded under the system. The majority of combustion-related emissions (about 82%) originate from electricity generation. The share of electricity generated from various fuel types differs substantially among EU Member States, leading to notable differences in their emission profiles under the EU ETS1.

Figure 2-2 illustrates net electricity generation by fuel type, broken down by country for the year 2024 and sorted by the share of conventional thermal generation in the electricity generation mix. Countries with a higher reliance on conventional thermal power generation typically report higher shares of emissions within the EU ETS1, while those utilizing nuclear, hydro, or renewable energy sources have significantly lower emissions from this sector.

It is important to note that while some Member States may have a high relative share of fossil-based electricity generation, their absolute emissions can still be comparatively low.

Figure 2-2 Net electricity generation by fuel type and country in 2024 (%)

Source: Eurostat (2025)

In 2024, combustion installations emitted a total of 589 Mt CO₂, compared to 650 Mt in 2023. Figure 2- presents the emissions trend of EU ETS1 combustion installations between 2021 and 2024, disaggregated by fuel type.⁵ Emissions from power plants declined by 55 Mt CO₂ in 2024 compared to the previous year. The largest reductions occurred at lignite-fired power plants (-17 Mt CO₂) and hard coal-fired power plants (-32 Mt CO₂). Gas-fired power plants reported 6 Mt CO₂ less than in 2023. Emissions from other combustion installations, including district heating plants and industrial heat production outside of identified industrial activities, decreased by approximately 13 Mt CO₂ compared to the previous year.

⁵ Since power plants are not explicitly identified in the Union Registry, their classification and fuel assignment were carried out manually based on the methodology described in Hermann et al. (2021).

Figure 2-3 Emissions of combustion installations

Source: DG CLIMA (2025c; 2025d) based on methodology developed in Hermann et al. (2021)

Figure 2-3 examines the changes in emissions from power plants in the countries with the highest power-related emissions (Germany, Poland, Italy, Czechia, Spain). In 2024, these five countries accounted for nearly 75 % of CO₂ emissions from all power plants covered by the EU ETS1. Emission reductions were observed across all of them. In Germany and Poland, emissions from coal-fired power plants (hard coal and lignite) decreased by a combined total of approximately 23 Mt CO₂ and 5.5 Mt CO₂ respectively. Together, these reductions represent nearly half of the total decrease in emissions from coal-fired power generation. A more detailed analysis of emission trends from power plants in other countries is provided in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4 Emissions from power plants by fuel in selected Member States (2023–2024)

Source: DG CLIMA (2025c; 2025d) based on methodology developed in Hermann et al. (2021)

Figure 2-5 illustrates the long-term development of EU ETS1 emissions from power plants by fuel type and country from 2005 to 2024. Emission trends continue to show significant differences between Member States. Several countries, including Luxembourg and Portugal, have reduced their power sector emissions by more than 90 % since 2005. Finland and Austria by more than 80%. Denmark, Spain, France, Sweden, Greece and Romania have also achieved substantial reductions of over 70 %. By contrast, emission reductions in some other countries remain comparatively modest, with Cyprus reporting a 7 % decrease and Lithuania a 23 % decrease in emissions from power generation over the same period.

Figure 2-5 Emissions of power plants by fuels and by country in Mt CO₂ (2023–2024)

Note: No fossil power plants in Iceland and Liechtenstein. Bulgaria and Romania joined in 2007, Croatia in 2013. Great Britain left in 2020 but Northern Ireland remained in the EU-ETS1. Since 2020, Sweden reports the emissions from the blast furnace power plant under activity code 24

Source: DG CLIMA (2025c; 2025d) based on methodology developed in Hermann et al. (2021)

Table 2-2 provides context for the decline in emissions from fossil-based power generation in 2024. Compared to the previous year, generation from fossil fuel sources decreased by 76 TWh, with significant reductions in coal and gas-fired generation (-37 and -35 TWh, respectively). Several key factors contributed to this development:

- Increased generation from low-carbon sources: Nuclear output rose by nearly 30 TWh in total, mainly driven by improved availability in France. However, nuclear generation declined in almost all other countries, with the notable exception of Sweden. Wind and solar generation increased by 45 TWh combined, and hydro output rebounded by 43 TWh after a dry period in previous years.
- Higher electricity demand: Electricity consumption increased by 32 TWh in 2024. Nevertheless, the strong expansion of low-emission generation more than met this additional demand, allowing fossil-based generation to decline further.
- Country-specific developments: Portugal achieved the largest relative emissions reduction in the power sector (-42 %), due to a sharp decline in fossil generation and a strong increase in hydro output. France also recorded a notable drop (-19 %), driven by lower gas use and a substantial recovery in nuclear generation. Croatia (-23 %) and Finland (-19 %) also showed marked reductions in fossil generation.

Table 2-2 Change in emissions from electricity generation, electricity consumption and generated amounts by fuel (2023-2024)

	Change in emissions 2024 vs. 2023*	Consumption on 2024 vs. 2023 [TWh]	Net electricity generation [TWh]									Net Import
			Total	of which **		Nuclear	Hydro	Wind	Solar			
				Thermal	Coal					Gas		
Total	-9.6%	31.8	51.5	-76.1	-37.3	-35.2	29.8	42.5	8.4	45.2		
PT	-41.7%	1.0	1.7	-5.1	N/A	-5.2	N/A	3.7	1.2	1.9	0.2	
HR	-22.7%	0.5	-2.1	-1.1	-0.5	-0.6	N/A	-1.4	0.1	0.3	2.8	
FI	-19.4%	2.8	1.5	-1.9	-1.1	0.0	-1.6	-0.9	5.4	0.5	1.4	
BG	-19.3%	0.9	-1.4	-2.4	-2.5	0.1	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1.8	2.3	
FR	-18.6%	-2.2	41.6	-13.8	-1.9	-13.5	41.3	16.3	-3.8	1.7	-39.4	
EE	-18.4%	0.0	0.4	-0.4	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.0	0.4	0.4	-0.4	
SK	-17.1%	-1.3	-0.1	-0.5	-0.6	0.6	-0.1	0.4	N/A	0.1	0.5	
IT	-15.9%	6.2	6.5	-11.5	-1.1	-9.2	N/A	13.8	-1.3	5.5	-0.3	
ES	-13.5%	2.9	-0.1	-12.6	-0.9	-11.5	-2.2	9.5	-1.6	6.8	3.7	
CZ	-12.7%	0.6	-2.0	-2.9	-3.2	0.1	-0.7	0.2	0.0	1.4	2.5	
BE	-11.6%	2.0	-6.9	-4.4	0.4	-4.3	-1.6	0.0	-1.4	0.7	8.7	
DE	-9.4%	1.3	-14.8	-16.3	-18.8	2.2	-6.7	3.3	-5.1	10.0	17.1	
DK	-9.2%	1.7	1.5	-0.2	0.7	0.0	N/A	0.0	1.2	0.5	0.6	
MT	-7.6%	0.2	-0.2	-0.2	N/A	-0.2	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.0	0.3	
LT	-7.3%	0.1	1.7	0.7	N/A	0.1	N/A	0.0	0.8	0.0	-1.5	
HU	-5.8%	1.9	2.5	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	2.4	-0.4	
PL	-5.5%	1.1	2.7	-2.1	-4.9	2.8	N/A	-0.6	1.6	3.8	-2.4	
NO	-5.1%	5.1	3.2	-0.3	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.7	0.6	0.3	-0.7	
IE	-4.3%	1.2	-0.4	-0.4	-0.3	-0.2	N/A	-0.1	-0.2	0.3	1.8	
RO	-4.0%	1.5	-4.4	-0.5	-1.0	0.5	-0.3	-4.2	-1.2	1.7	6.0	
AT	-2.2%	0.8	7.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	N/A	4.1	1.2	N/A	-6.7	
LU	-1.8%	0.3	0.3	0.1	N/A	0.0	N/A	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	
IS	-1.8%	-2.2	-2.3	0.0	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.8	0.0	0.0	N/A	
NL	-0.9%	3.3	2.0	-2.9	-0.5	-1.9	-0.4	0.0	3.5	1.7	1.4	
LV	4.5%	0.2	-0.1	0.1	N/A	0.2	N/A	-0.6	0.0	0.4	0.3	
SE	4.8%	1.8	6.6	-1.7	0.0	0.0	2.1	-1.4	6.5	1.0	-4.9	
CY	5.4%	0.4	0.4	0.1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.0	0.2	N/A	
GR	8.2%	-0.4	5.2	3.8	-1.3	4.9	N/A	-0.7	0.9	1.2	-5.2	
SI	11.8%	0.4	1.3	0.4	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.5	-0.9	
LI***												
XI***	-7%											

Note: * Combustion installations (Activity Code 20)
 ** Additional thermal electricity generation is reported by Eurostat from oil, renewable and non-renewables, which are not shown here.
 *** No data for Liechtenstein (LI) and Northern Ireland (XI) available

Source: EEA (2025b), Eurostat (2025)

Table 2-3 lists the 30 power plants with the highest verified CO₂ emissions under the EU ETS1 for the year 2024. The data are based on verified emissions reported in the Union Registry (previously EUTL) and matched with actual generation data from ENTSO-E. Fuel types were assigned according to the methodology by Hermann et al. (2021).

The ranking continues to be dominated by lignite fired power plants. Bełchatów in Poland remains the largest single emitter with 27.2 Mt of CO₂, showing a 4 % increase compared to the previous year. Neurath, Jänschwalde, and Niederaußem in Germany follow in the top four, despite recording significant reductions in emissions. Together, these installations account for more than 16 % of total emissions from power generation in the EU ETS1.

While some facilities such as Boxberg IV and Weisweiler reported notable increases in emissions, others like Schwarze Pumpe and Opole showed marked declines. The composition of the top 30 also reflects the ongoing presence of hard coal and blast furnace gas as relevant fuels in several Member States.

Emission intensities range from approximately 0.85 to 1.3 t CO₂ per megawatt hour for lignite and hard coal plants, consistent with historical values. For blast furnace gas plants, no emission intensity is reported due to data limitations. Changes in ranking compared to the previous year reflect shifts in dispatch patterns, operational hours or the return of reserve capacity.

Among the top 30 installations in 2024, 19 primarily used lignite, seven were hard coal based and four reported blast furnace gas as the main fuel. These 30 power plants emitted a total of 191 Mt of CO₂, with the largest shares originating from Germany (45 %) and Poland (34 %). Together, these two countries accounted for nearly 80 % of emissions from the top 30. Other notable contributions came from Czechia (7 %) and Bulgaria (4 %), while the remaining countries each accounted for 2 % or less. This concentration reflects the regional distribution of high emitting coal and lignite capacity within the EU ETS1.

Table 2-3 Top 30 emitters in 2024 (power plants)

Rank 2023-2024	EUTL ID	Company	Power Plant	Main Fuel	Verified		Emission intensity 2024* (t CO ₂ / MWh)
					Emissions 2024 (Mt CO ₂)	Change 2023- 2024	
1 =	PL 1	PGE	Bełchatów	Lignite	27,2	4%	1,14
2 =	DE 1606	RWE	Neurath	Lignite	13,4	-19%	1,05
3 =	DE 1456	LEAG	Jänschwalde	Lignite	12,1	-13%	1,26
4 =	DE 1649	RWE	Niederaußem	Lignite	11,8	-11%	1,13
5 ↑(6)	DE 1607	RWE	Weisweiler	Lignite	10,3	12%	1,25
6 ↑(7)	PL 4	ENEA	Kozienice	Hard coal	9,1	2%	0,92
7 ↑(9)	PL 3	PGE	Turów	Lignite	8,2	-7%	1,28
8 ↓(5)	DE 1459	LEAG	Schwarze Pumpe	Lignite	8,1	-16%	1,14
9 ↑(11)	DE 1454	LEAG	Boxberg Werk IV	Lignite	8,0	18%	1,02
10 ↓(8)	PL 2	PGE	Opole	Hard coal	7,3	-19%	0,87
11 ↑(12)	DE 1453	LEAG	Boxberg Werk III	Lignite	5,8	-7%	1,18
12 ↓(10)	DE 1460	LEAG	Lippendorf	Lignite	5,7	-23%	0,96
13 ↑(14)	BG 50	TPP	Maritsa East 2	Lignite	5,1	19%	1,14
14 ↓(13)	PL 5	Enea	Połaniec	Hard coal	4,8	-6%	0,74
15 ↑(19)	BE 750	Electrabel	Knippegroen	blast furnace gas	4,6	20%	-
16 ↑(17)	DE 1376	Uniper	Kraftwerk Schkopau	Lignite	4,3	9%	1,29
17 ↑(20)	NL 188	Nuon Power Generation B.V.	Nuon Power Velsen	blast furnace gas	4,1	12%	-
18 ↓(16)	ES 201	EDP	Aboño 1	Hard coal	4,0	-1%	1,50
19 ↑(21)	CZ 129	CEZ	Elektrarna Tusimice 2	Lignite	3,7	5%	0,93
20 ↓(15)	CZ 124	Sev.en Energie	Elektrarna Pocerady	Lignite	3,7	-11%	1,05
21 ↑(26)	DE 1132	Salzgitter Flachstahl	Kraftwerk Hallendorf	blast furnace gas	3,5	11%	-
22 ↑(28)	CZ 127	CEZ	Elektrarna Prunerov 2	Lignite	3,5	14%	0,96
23 ↑(27)	PL 31	TAMEH Polska	Zakład Wytwarzania Nowa	blast furnace gas	3,4	10%	-
24 ↓(23)	DE 1380	Großkraftwerk Mannheim	Mannheim	Hard coal	3,1	-8%	1,04
25 ↑(37)	SI 4	TERMOELEKTRARNA	Termoelektrarna Sostanj	Lignite	3,1	13%	1,01
26 ↓(18)	PL 209933	ENEA	Kozienice Block 11	hard coal	3,1	-20%	0,85
27 ↑(29)	HU 142	RWE	Mátra Eromu ZRt.	Lignite	2,9	-3%	1,22
28 ↑(30)	PL 27	PGNiG TERMIKA	ELEKTROCIÉPLOWNIA SIEKIERKI	Hard coal	2,8	-4%	1,73
29 ↑(41)	BG 152	AES-3C Maritza East 1	TPP AES-3C Maritza East 1	Lignite	2,7	6%	1,20
30 ↑(33)	CZ 121	CEZ	Elektrarna Ledvice	Lignite	2,7	-3%	1,05

Note: All installations are power plants reporting under the activity code combustion in the EUTL. Values in brackets show the ranking from the previous year
*Emission intensity of blast furnace installations not calculated due to unclear electricity generation data (LI) and Northern Ireland (XI) available

Source: DG CLIMA (2025c; 2025d) based on methodology developed in Hermann et al. (2021), ENTSO-E (2025)

2.1.2 Industry

Figure 2-6 examines emissions trends from industrial installations (activity code 21-99) in the EU ETS1 since 2013, the start of the third trading period in the EU ETS1. Industrial emissions covered by the EU ETS1 fell by 16.8 % between 2013 and 2024, while combustion emissions decreased by 55.6 % over the same time period, leading to an overall reduction of stationary emissions of 45.8 %.

Industrial emissions under the EU ETS1 were relatively stable from 2013 until 2019. In 2020, emissions in the cement and lime, iron and steel, and refineries sectors, fell as a result of the reduced outputs and overall reduced economic activity during the COVID-19 pandemic (see Figure 2-6). Emissions in the cement and lime and iron and steel sector quickly recovered to pre-pandemic levels in 2021. However, since 2021 total industrial emissions showed a more pronounced decline compared to the decade before. The decrease in emissions did not necessarily reflect a shift towards cleaner technologies but was mainly driven by surging natural gas prices in Europe amidst the Russian invasion of Ukraine, which led to marginal efficiency gains and reduced production outputs. The largest relative emission reductions from 2021 to 2024 occurred in the pulp and paper sector, the other non-metallic minerals sector, and the other metals (incl. aluminium) sector, with 23.9 %, 20.0 %, and 19.6 %, respectively. Emissions in the chemicals sector declined from 2021 to 2023 as a result of the stark reduction in ammonia production due to high gas prices, only from 2023 to 2024 production slowly picked up again leading to an increase in emissions.

From 2023 to 2024 total industrial EU ETS1 emissions decreased only slightly by 2.4 Mt CO₂-eq, which translates into a reduction of 0.5 % from 2023 levels. The largest relative emission reductions were observed in the cement and lime, and other non-metallic minerals sector with a 3.8 % and 3.4 % year-on-year emissions reduction, respectively. The decrease in emissions by these sectors was partially offset by an increase in emissions in the chemical and other metals sectors. Emissions in the chemical sector increased by 6.4 % from 2023 to 2024.

Figure 2-6 Industry emissions by sector (2013–2024)

Note: For groupings of industrial sectors see Table A-1Table A-12 in Annex. The blue dotted line reflects emissions from the iron and steel sector including emissions from combustion installations using blast furnace gas.

Source: EEA (2025b)

The cement and lime, iron and steel, refineries, and chemicals sector are the highest emitting industrial sectors covered under the ETS1 in 2024. Together they accounted for 86.8 % of industrial emissions and for 32.5 % of the total EU ETS1 emissions.

Figure 2-7 shows the share of industrial emissions by sector for each Member State in 2024. The shares of emissions from different industrial sectors vary significantly between EEA countries. The cement and lime sector is responsible for more than 90 % of the total industrial emissions in Cyprus and Ireland. In Estonia there is no cement and lime production, and the majority of emissions originate in the refineries sector. Half of the Member States have less than 5 % of industrial emissions originating from the chemicals sector, whereas in countries like Hungary and the Netherlands chemical emissions account for 59.4 % and 38.6 % of the emission in 2024, respectively. The largest emission shares of the iron and steel sector are recorded in Austria and Finland. Norway and Iceland report their largest industrial emission shares in the other metals sector. Emissions in this sector primarily originate from aluminium production. Especially primary aluminium production requires a large amount of electricity. If electricity is generated by fossil fuels, production costs are substantially higher due to added CO₂ costs. Making it more economically viable to produce aluminium in countries like Iceland or Norway where most of the electricity is cheaper and generated from renewable sources like large hydropower and geothermal installations.

Figure 2-7 Industry emissions by sector and Member State (2024)

Note: No installations from industrial sectors reported emissions in Malta, Northern Ireland and Lichtenstein

Source: EEA (2025b)

Figure 2-8 shows the relative emission reductions of all industrial sectors compared to the relative decline of the EU ETS1-wide cap. Between 2014 and 2019 the change in industrial emissions compared to the base year of 2013 was predominantly positive, meaning industrial emissions increased in nearly all years.

From 2020 onwards, industrial emissions were lower than base year values in each year. The emission reductions depicted in Figure 2-8 are the results of external shocks and energy efficiency gains. The reduction of 7.7 % in 2020 compared to 2013 levels reflects the economic shock of the COVID-19 pandemic. Emission reductions in 2022, 2023, and 2024 between 8.8 % and 16.8 % reflect the reduced production outputs and energy efficiency gains due to the gas price increase of the energy crisis after the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

The decline in emissions in the industrial sector alone is not a good indicator of decarbonisation efforts made by industry as it is skewed by a decline in production. In contrast, the change in benchmarking values is expressed in emission intensity values and takes production levels into account, which gives a better indication of actual abatement efforts made. Benchmark values are renewed every five years and reflect the emission intensity of the top 10 % most efficient installations producing a product covered by the EU ETS1 (EC 2021). The next set of benchmarks values will be published for the period 2026 to 2030.

If the benchmark values are set at lower levels for the next period, this means that the top 10 % efficient installations decreased their emission intensities. Benchmark values set for the period 2021 to 2025 were lower than those for the period 2013 to 2020. In some sectors emission intensities fell faster than in others, reflecting the different abatement challenges in each sector. For example, the benchmark value for grey cement clinker fell from 0.766 to 0.693 t CO₂-eq per t product, which equals a 10 % reduction. Whereas the benchmark value for electric arc furnace carbon steel fell by 24 % (EC 2021).

Even with external shocks that lowered production levels and therefore emissions, emission reductions observed in industrial sectors were not in line with the reduction path of the EU ETS1 cap. In 2024, emission would have needed to be reduced at twice the actual rate to align with the cap reduction path. As combustion installations decreased emissions faster than the cap's reduction path, overall emissions remain within the system-wide cap. The EU ETS1 allows regulated entities to trade EUAs freely, enabling the cheapest mitigation option to be realised first. These have historically been mainly in the combustion sector. In the foreseeable future, industrial emissions will be responsible for most emissions within the EU ETS1 and will have to increase decarbonisation efforts to ensure overall emissions stay within the cap.

Figure 2-8 Relative industrial emissions reductions compared to the cap (2014–2024)

Note: 2013 reflects the base year

Source: EEA (2025b)

Unlike combustion installations, industrial installations have historically received free allowances for the majority of their verified emissions to protect against the risk of carbon leakage (see section 1.3.2 for further details). Carbon leakage refers to the relocation of businesses or operations from countries and regions with climate policies and their associated costs to regions without comparable climate policies. This relocation can result in an increase of total global GHG emissions which is referred to as carbon leakage. Figure 2-9 shows the development of emissions and free allocation for the cement and lime, iron and steel, refineries and chemical sector. Free allocation of allowances declines in line with emissions regardless of whether they decrease due to lower output or ambitious mitigation efforts. Until now industries were only partially exposed to the CO₂ price, for example in 2024, 98.6 % of the emissions from the cement and lime sector were covered by free allocation⁶.

⁶ The EU ETS Directive requires adjustments of free allocation in line with production levels. Hence, it is expected that free allocation is reduced with a delay.

Figure 2-9 Industry emissions versus free allocation (2021-2024)

Note: The iron and steel sector emissions include emissions from combustion installations using blast furnace gas. For iron and steel sector emissions without waste gas emissions see Figure 2-6.

Source: EEA (2025b)

Starting in 2026, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) will gradually replace free allocation as a carbon leakage protection measure for some sectors. Initially CBAM will replace free allocation stepwise in the cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertiliser, and hydrogen sector. CBAM aims to protect European industry against the risk of carbon leakage by putting an equivalent carbon price on imports of goods from selected sectors. Importers of those products have to surrender CBAM obligations covering the embedded emissions of the imported goods. This way CBAM aims to ensure that EU producers and non-EU producers face similar carbon costs, which reduces the risk of carbon leakage and increase the competitiveness of European producers. The current CBAM Regulation limits the scope of CBAM to direct emissions for most sectors, only for imports of the cement and fertiliser sector CBAM applies to both direct and indirect emissions⁷ (CBAM Regulation 2023).

CBAM entered a transitional period in October 2023, during which importers had to already start reporting their emissions. The definitive period will begin in 2026 as of which CBAM will be slowly phased in until it fully replaces free allocation for the covered sectors by 2034.

The CBAM factor which is the share of emissions subject to CBAM in each year increases annually and mirrors the phase out of free allocation (see Figure 2-10). In 2025 sectors covered by CBAM still receive 100 % of their share of free allocation which is determined by the benchmark value. In 2026 installations

⁷ Direct emissions refer to emissions directly released in the production process, whereas indirect emissions refer to emissions from the electricity used in the production process.

receive only 97.5 %, which is equal to 100 % minus the CBAM factor of 2.5 %, in 2027 they receive only 95 % of their share of free allocation and so forth until the CBAM factor reaches 100 % in 2034.

Figure 2-10 CBAM phase-in and free allocation phase-out

Source: Own illustration based on the Directive (EU) 2023/959 2024)

Importers will not only have to surrender CBAM obligations for the emissions covered by the CBAM share but also for the difference between their emissions and the benchmark value multiplied by the CBAM share. This increases the carbon leakage protection from CBAM, as imports that have an emissions intensity higher than the benchmark will have to surrender CBAM obligations slightly higher than the CBAM factor taking into account the share of allowances that EU installations currently already do not receive free allocation for.

2.2 Transport under the EU ETS1

The EU ETS1 covers greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from certain transport modes through the direct inclusion of their operators. Aviation has been part of the system since 2012, with compliance obligations applying from 2013. The scope was modified in 2013 following the “Stop-the-Clock” decision, which temporarily limited coverage to flights within the European Economic Area (EEA) instead of all international routes to and from the EEA. This measure, intended to facilitate negotiations under the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) on a global market-based mechanism, has remained in place in adapted form.

From 2024, maritime transport has also been included in the EU ETS1. The rules apply to CO₂ emissions from ships of 5000 gross tonnage (GT) and above on intra-EEA voyages, at berth and to 50 % of emissions from voyages between the EEA and third countries. This marks a substantial expansion of the EU ETS1 to a major transport mode previously outside its scope.

It is important to distinguish transport emissions covered by the EU ETS1 from those under the EU ETS2, which will start in 2027 and cover CO₂ emissions from the combustion of fuels in road transport, buildings and additional sectors not included in EU ETS1. In EU ETS2, the compliance obligation lies with fuel suppliers rather than with the transport operators (see chapter 4).

2.2.1 Aviation

In 2024, emissions from aviation under the EU ETS1 continued to rise. Total reported emissions increased by 15% compared to 2023 and reached 64.1 million tonnes of CO₂. This development reflects the ongoing post pandemic recovery in air transport activity that has been observed in recent years.

Within the EU ETS1 scope, aviation operators reported 61.5 million tonnes of CO₂ in 2024. A further 1.1 million tonnes of CO₂ were reported in the Swiss ETS for flights under the EU ETS1 scope, while 0.7 million tonnes of CO₂ were reported in the EU ETS1 for flights under the Swiss ETS scope

At the same time, the total supply of EU Aviation Allowances (EUAAAs) decreased. Free allocation to aviation operators fell by 22% to 19.0 million EUAAAs. Allocations from the New Entrants Reserve were zero. Auctioned volumes increased to 6.7 million EUAAAs, which is an increase of 17%. The annual supply and demand balance widened from -31.3 million EUAAAs in 2023 to -45.1 million EUAAAs in 2024. This underlines the growing reliance of the aviation sector on allowances from the stationary sector. The average EUAA Price declined by 21% to EUR 64.8. This decline reflects the broader carbon market development, as EUAA prices closely follow those of EU Allowances (EUA) under the ETS1 system.

Table 2-4 EUAA demand, supply and price for aviation operators (2023-2024)

	2023	2024	Change 2023-2024
Total demand (Mt CO₂)	55.8	64.1	15%
Aviation emissions EU-ETS1	53.5	61.5	15%
Reported in Swiss-ETS for EU-ETS1 scope	0.9	1.1	23%
Reported in EU-ETS1 for Swiss-ETS scope	0.7	0.7	1%
Reported in Swiss-ETS for Swiss-ETS scope	0.8	0.9	21%
Total supply (millions of EUAAAs)	24.5	19.0	-22%
Aviation free allocation	17.2	10.9	-37%
Aviation free allocation (NER)	-	-	-
Auctioned amounts	5.7	6.7	17%
Allocation in Swiss-ETS for EU-ETS1 scope	0.4	0.3	-26%
Allocation in EU-ETS1 for Swiss-ETS scope	0.5	0.3	-28%
Allocation in Swiss-ETS for Swiss-ETS scope	0.5	0.4	-24%
Swiss auctioned amounts	0.2	0.4	136%
Annual supply-demand balance (millions of EUAAAs)	-31.3	-45.1	44%
Average EUAA price* (EUR)	82.3	64.8	-21%

Notes: NER, New Entrants Reserve.

Sources: EC (2025b), EEA (2025b), EEX (2025), FOEN (2025), FOEN (2025)

The time series of verified emissions for aviation operators from 2013 to 2024 shows a steady increase from the start of the EU ETS1 until 2019, with only minor year-on-year variations (see Figure 2-11). In 2020 and 2021, verified emissions declined sharply due to the significant reduction in air traffic following the COVID-19 pandemic. From 2022 onwards, emissions increased again and in 2024 they were close to the highest levels observed before 2020.

The annual cap for aviation, which is the total quantity of emission allowances available, was set based on the average verified emissions of the years 2004 to 2006, adjusted by a factor of 0.95. It remained constant at 38 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent between 2013 and 2020. In 2021, the cap was adjusted to account for Brexit, including the reduced scope as flights from the UK were no longer covered by the EU ETS1. Since 2021 the linear reduction factor is also applied to the cap for aviation. Thus, the cap was reduced to 27 million tonnes of CO₂. In 2024, the cap increased slightly due to the inclusion of flights to and from the outermost regions⁸. In almost all years since 2013, except for 2020 and 2021, verified emissions were above the cap. This required the aviation sector to acquire additional allowances from the wider EU ETS1 market, where emission reductions are often achieved at lower cost in other sectors.

In early 2024 the European Commission adopted rules for a support mechanism designed to accelerate the use of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) in commercial aviation (DG CLIMA 2025b). The mechanism aims to partially or fully offset the price difference between fossil kerosene and SAF, with funding provided through the EU ETS1. For this purpose, 20 million EU ETS1 allowances, with an estimated value of around EUR 1.6 billion, have been reserved as of 1 January 2024. Airlines were required to report their 2024 fuel use by 31 March 2025. The Commission subsequently published the official price differences between fossil kerosene and SAF in May 2025. Based on these data, the Commission decided in August 2025 on the allocation of allowances under the mechanism. In September 2025, it announced that approximately 1.3 million allowances (worth about EUR 100 million) had been distributed to 53 airlines.⁹

Since 2013, the scope of the EU ETS1 for aviation has been limited to flights within the EEA and flights between the EEA and Switzerland. This limitation was introduced after the EU decided in 2012 to suspend the inclusion of all international flights in the system, following opposition from third countries and the launch of negotiations in the ICAO to establish a global market-based measure. These negotiations resulted in the adoption of the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA), which started with a pilot phase in 2021 and applies to international flights between participating states outside the EU ETS1 scope. Under CORSIA, operators must offset the growth in their CO₂ emissions above a defined baseline for international flights between participating states that are not covered by the EU ETS1, by purchasing and cancelling eligible emission units from approved carbon crediting programmes. Airlines can also reduce their offset obligations by using SAF.

⁸ The “outermost regions” refer to territories that are part of EU Member States but geographically distant from mainland Europe, such as the Azores, Madeira, the Canary Islands, and several French overseas departments. Until 2023, flights to and from these regions were exempted from the EU ETS; they have been included since 2024, leading to a slight increase in the aviation cap.

⁹ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-other-reads/news/eu-allocates-eu100m-worth-ets-allowances-help-airlines-buy-sustainable-aviation-fuels-2025-09-17_en

Figure 2-11 Verified Emissions: Aviation operators (2005–2024)

Source: EU (2020), EEA (2025b)

Table 2-5 presents the top 10 emitters in the aviation sector in 2024 based on a consolidated operator approach, grouping individual airlines under their parent companies. Several entries therefore represent corporate groups rather than single carriers — for example, Austrian Airlines, Brussels Airlines, Eurowings and Swiss are included under Lufthansa Group, while British Airways, Iberia and Vueling are aggregated under International Airlines Group. This approach avoids fragmentation of emissions among subsidiaries and provides a clearer representation of the largest emitting corporate entities in the aviation sector.

In 2024, verified emissions from aviation under the EU ETS1 totalled 61.4 Mt CO₂, an increase of 15 % compared with 2023. Free allocation amounted to 17.2 million EUAs, covering 28 % of total emissions. Ryanair remained the largest emitter with 12.1 Mt CO₂ (+17 %), followed by Lufthansa Group (7.8 Mt, +11 %) and Air France-KLM (5.6 Mt, +9 %). The International Airlines Group ranked fourth (5.2 Mt, +5 %), ahead of EasyJet (4.0 Mt, +15 %) and Wizz Air Group (3.1 Mt, +11 %). Norwegian recorded the largest relative increase among the top 10 (+21 %), while TAP Air Portugal and Aegean Airlines each reported emissions of 1.1 Mt. The “Other” category, comprising all remaining operators, accounted for 17.5 Mt CO₂ (+24 %).

Table 2-5 Top 10 emitters in aviation in 2024

	Verified Emissions EU-ETS1 in 2024 (Mt CO ₂)	Compared to 2023	Allocated (millions of EUAAs)	Share of free allocations in 2024
Ryanair	12.1	+17%	3.3	27%
Lufthansa Group	7.8	+11%	2.2	28%
Air France-KLM	5.6	+9%	1.6	28%
International Airlines Group	5.2	+5%	1.5	29%
Easyjet	4.0	+15%	1.1	28%
Wizz Air Group	3.1	+11%	0.9	28%
SAS	1.8	+5%	0.5	28%
Norwegian	2.0	+21%	0.6	27%
TAP Air Portugal	1.1	+1%	0.3	30%
Aegean Airlines	1.1	+11%	0.3	27%
Other	17.5	+24%	4.9	28%
Total Aviation	61.4	+15%	17.2	28%

Note: Lufthansa Group: Deutsche Lufthansa, Austrian Airlines, Brussels Airlines, Lufthansa Cargo, Air Dolomiti, Eurowings, EW Discover, Edelweis Air, Luftahnsa Technik, Swiss Air
 Air France-KLM: Air France, KLM, Transavia Airlines
 International Airlines Group: Vueling Airlines, British Airways, Iberia, Aer Lingus
 Edelweiss Air and Swiss Air report their emissions in the Swiss ETS. Their emissions are therefore not included here

Source: DG CLIMA (2025c; 2025d)

2.2.2 Maritime

The EU ETS1 was extended to include maritime transport starting in 2024 as part of the broader "Fit for 55" package. The extension covers CO₂ emissions from ships of 5,000 gross tonnage (GT) and above on voyages within the EEA, at berth and on 50% of international ingoing and outgoing voyages.

2024 is the first reporting year of verified CO₂ emissions for shipping companies covered by the extension of the EU ETS1 to maritime transport. Initially, only a share of the verified emissions will be subject to the surrender obligation: in 2024, shipping companies need to surrender allowances for 40% of their verified emissions. This share increases to 100% by 2026. In contrast to aviation, allowances for maritime transport are fully auctioned from the first year onwards. The inclusion of maritime transport into the EU ETS1 cap increased the total number of allowances by 78.4 million in 2024 with a retrospective application of the LRF. Since 2018, shipping companies were already required to report CO₂ emissions data on EU-related maritime transport through the EU shipping MRV system. More details on the EU ETS1 extension to maritime transport can be found in the previous Trends and Projections report (see Nissen et al. 2024) and in the factsheet by Wissner and Cames (2023).

Table 2-6 shows the demand and supply for the maritime transport within the EU ETS1. There are no maritime-sector specific allowances and shipping companies covered their demand in the first reporting period with EUAs. On 16 September 2025, the Union Registry showed verified emissions of 89.9 million tonnes of CO₂. However, the data in the registry is still subject to change. In the weeks prior, significant fluctuations in verified emissions were observed. For the purpose of this report, a data snapshot as of 16 September 2025 was used.

Table 2-6 Demand & supply for maritime operators (2023-2024)

	2023	2024	Change 2023-2024
Total demand (Mt CO₂)	-	89.9	-

Notes: No free allocation for maritime operators. Maritime ETS started in 2024.

Sources: EEA/European Environment Agency (2025b)

Verified emissions for 2024 are broadly in line with the trends observed in previous years under the EU MRV system, as shown in the figure below. Emissions within the scope of the EU ETS1 ranged between 80 and 90 million tonnes of CO₂ in recent years and did not fluctuate significantly. Changes over time are mainly attributable to the COVID-19 pandemic, the UK’s withdrawal from the EU and Russia’s invasion of Ukraine. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was less pronounced than in the aviation sector (cf. Section 2.2.1).

Figure 2-12 Verified Emissions: Shipping companies (2018–2024)

Notes: Own estimates of ETS1 scope emissions for years before 2024 based on MRV data and using 50% of emissions reported for international voyages.

Sources: EMSA (2024)

Figure 2-13 shows that maritime emissions covered by the EU ETS1 are not distributed evenly among Member States. With over 10 MtCO₂ emissions Greece, Italy and Spain have the largest share of total emissions.

Figure 2-13 Maritime emissions by member state (2024)

Sources: EEA European Environment Agency (2025b)

3 Projections and Policy Impacts

This section discusses expected developments of emissions from stationary installations, aviation and maritime transport, covered by EU ETS1. For this purpose, the latest projections submitted under Article 18 of the Governance Regulation¹⁰ are considered for EU countries¹¹. Iceland and Norway submitted WEM and WAM projections in 2025, too.

3.1 Stationary

Key messages:

- **Projected Reductions in Stationary Emissions:** Projected emission reductions are considerably higher compared to last year's projections: By 2030, stationary emissions in the EU ETS1 are expected to decrease by 61.7 % compared to 2005 in a scenario with existing measures, or by 65.3 % if additional measures are implemented. According to these estimates, the total EU ETS1 target of a 62 % reduction by 2030 compared to 2005 could be achieved. This target includes the whole EU ETS1 scope, covering aviation and maritime emissions, as well as stationary installations.
- **Meeting the 2050 Climate Goals:** Even in the scenario with additional measures, stationary EU ETS1 emissions are projected to be at about 390 Mt CO₂-eq in 2050, which corresponds to a reduction of 81.1% compared to 2005 levels by 2050. This will not be sufficient to meet the EU climate neutrality target for 2050, as emissions from some of the sectors outside of the EU ETS1 are expected to be harder to abate than stationary EU ETS1 emissions.
- **Country-Specific Projections:** Emission projections vary widely across EU Member States. Some countries, such as Sweden, Cyprus and Poland anticipate significant reductions of EU ETS1 emissions until 2030. The effect of increased electricity demand without the parallel increase of electricity production from renewable energy in scenarios with additional measures leads to lower projected emission reductions, which is the case in projections for Czechia, Germany, and Latvia.
- **Sector-Specific Trends:** The energy industry is projected to continue driving emission reductions in the EU ETS1 until 2030, although the pace of reduction will slow after that point. Industrial processes and manufacturing are expected to see more modest declines in emissions, with little change projected after 2040.
- **Future of the EU ETS1 Cap:** If the current linear reduction factor remains unchanged after 2030, the cap on EU ETS1 emissions reaches zero before 2040. But this scenario is neither aligned with projections from Member States, nor with projections made by the Commission in the context of the 2040 Impact Assessment. The Commission's upcoming EU ETS1 Review is expected to reflect on these challenges.

3.1.1 Overview

According to the latest emission projections under the 'with existing measures' (WEM) scenario, stationary emissions in the EU ETS1 are projected to decrease by 61.7 % until 2030 compared to 2005 levels. If additional measures are taken into account in a 'with additional measures' (WAM) scenario, emissions in stationary EU ETS1 sectors are projected to decrease by 65.3 % compared to 2005 (see

¹⁰ Governance Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R1999>

¹¹ All EU countries submitted GHG projections in 2025 but Bulgaria and Romania. For Romania, data was gap-filled based on their latest NECP submission. For Belgium, the 2024 submission was used and extrapolated to 2055.

Figure 3-1). This projected decrease is considerably higher than in previous projections. The targeted reduction of 62 % compared to 2005 levels for the overall EU ETS1 is within reach, even considering the contrasting trend of EU ETS1 transport emissions: Aviation emissions are projected to grow rather than contribute to the reduction (cf. Section 3.2) and maritime emissions are projected to stay relatively constant (cf. Section 3.3).

The annual average emission reduction in the next six years needs to be equal to 43 Mt CO₂-eq to reach the EU ETS1 reduction target in 2030. According to the average decrease of aggregated projections of 52 Mt CO₂-eq, (with existing) or 64 Mt CO₂-eq (with planned measures), EU ETS1 stationary emissions are projected to be on track to reach that target.

Figure 3-1 Historic and projected EU ETS1 emissions in stationary installations

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025.

The cap shown in this figure has been derived from the aggregated ETS1 cap, which is a cap including both stationary and maritime emissions.

Note: WEM means 'with existing measures'; WAM means 'with additional measures'
Historic stationary EU ETS emissions include scope estimates, excluding UK.

The difference between the WEM and WAM scenarios increases only slightly between 2030 and 2050. If additional measures are considered, the total emission reduction for EU ETS1 stationary installations adds up to 80.8 % until 2050 compared to 2005. This is eight percentage points lower compared to the previous projections but still far off the EU climate neutrality target for 2050.

The EU ETS1 cap was mainly designed to reflect the targeted emission reduction until 2030. If the current Linear Reduction Factor (LRF) is continued after 2030, the cap follows a linear path until it reaches zero before 2040. However, even in scenarios in which the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target is achieved, EU ETS1 emissions are projected to persist in the year 2040, e.g. in the 2040 Impact Assessment scenarios

(EC 2024). Under the current cap trajectory and if emissions develop as projected, there will be a shortage of EUAs from the mid 2030s onwards, even considering the historic surplus of EUAs in the market and the effects of the Market Stability Reserve (MSR). The next EU ETS Review, which is expected in 2026, will be important for the further development and functioning of the EU ETS1. The Review is expected to consider elements such as permanent carbon removals, a revision of the cap, as well as the functioning of the MSR.

3.1.2 Projection methodology and scenario updates

According to Art. 18 of the Governance Regulation, 2025 is a mandatory reporting year for GHG emission projections. As in former years, country projections are aggregated to EU ETS-wide projections by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) and its ETC/CM. 25 EU Member States, Norway, and Iceland submitted new GHG emission projections. These updates show a higher reduction ambition compared to previous projections: According to the latest projections with existing policies and measures (WEM scenario), stationary EU ETS1 emissions in 2030 are projected to be 17 % lower compared to last year's projections, and even lower in the longer term, e.g. – 24 % in 2050. Projections of stationary EU ETS1 emissions with planned and additional measures (WAM scenario), show a similar decline in emissions compared to last year's WAM projections.

Although projected emissions show a more ambitious picture overall, some countries project higher EU ETS1 emissions compared to last year's projections. Emission projections in the WAM scenario show higher projected ETS1 emissions for the year 2030 in Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Romania, Slovenia, and Spain.

The aggregated projection for EU 27, provided by the EEA and its ETC/CM use 2023 as the first year for their projections. For this year, a considerable gap of about 65 Mt CO₂-eq to actual emissions in the stationary sector can be observed (see Figure 3-1). For the year 2024 this gap increases to about 80 Mt CO₂-eq. This is the result of differing starting years of Member States' projections: For only seven Member States the reference year is 2023, while projections of five Member States use early starting years between 2019 and 2021.

For a complete picture on EU ETS1-wide projections some data had to be gap-filled: Belgium and Romania did not yet submit updated projections in 2025 and were gap-filled by the EEA and its ETC/CM. For Belgium, projections were gap-filled using the 2024 projections submission. For Romania, data were gap-filled by applying growth rates taken from the 2024 NECP submission. For the overview on EU ETS1 emissions in this report, projections in the WEM scenario were gap-filled for Northern Ireland from 2025 onwards and for Norway from 2040 onwards with the application of an average reduction rate¹². This also applies to the WAM projections of Northern Ireland and Norway from 2035 onwards. For Liechtenstein, no projections from previous years exist and no EU ETS1 emissions are reported since 2021, so no gap-filling is carried out.

Projections submitted in 2025 are the first ones which should fully take into account the latest revision of the EU ETS Directive that entered into force mid-2023. Recommended parameters for energy prices and CO₂ prices were made available in a guidance document by the European Commission in April 2024 (EC 2022a). While not mandatory, Member States are encouraged to use them in the elaboration of their projections. These parameters considered decreasing gas prices after the peak in 2022 due to the Russian invasion of Ukraine and the associated turmoil on global energy markets. After the decrease until 2024, there is a slight increase estimated for 2025, followed again by a downturn of gas prices until 2035. The EU ETS1 allowance price proposed to be used in projections for 2030 is 95 EUR/EUA, for both the WEM and the WAM scenario. In the WEM scenario, this price increases to 220 EUR/EUA in 2050 and in the WAM scenario this price increases to 520 EUR/EUA in 2055, both higher than in the recommendation of 2022.

¹² As Norway only submitted projections for every fifth year, gap-filling for in-between years has been applied in addition.

11 Member States used the EU ETS1 price from the guidance, considerably more than in projections in 2023 (2) and 2024 (5). In a similar fashion, the number of Member States which used the recommended parameters for coal, gas, and oil prices increased strongly.

3.1.3 Emission trends by country

In Figure 3-2, Member States, Norway and Iceland are sorted by historic changes of EU ETS1 emissions until 2024 compared to EU ETS1 emissions in 2005 (purple points), with Luxembourg showing the highest reduction (due to the closure of its biggest natural gas power station) while Iceland recorded increasing EU ETS1 emissions (due to the construction of new industrial installations such as for primary aluminum production).

Figure 3-2 Historic and projected changes until 2030 in stationary EU ETS1 emissions relative to 2005 emission levels

Note: Emissions of Liechtenstein decreased by 100% from 2005 to 2021 and are zero since then (not displayed). Emissions from 2005 to 2013 are adjusted to reflect the current scope of the EU ETS1. This alignment enables a consistent comparison over time by accounting for changes in scope, following the methodology established by Graichen et al. (2017).

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025

Additionally, the projected emission reductions from 2024 until 2030 are shown as green and orange bars. Under the WEM scenario, EU ETS1 emissions are expected to decline in most countries until 2030, with reductions ranging from 0.2% for Lithuania to 29.9% for Sweden. There are two countries that anticipate increases in their EU ETS1 emissions between 2024 (as projected) and 2030 based upon their WEM projections - Croatia and Iceland. Croatia projects to decrease its EU ETS1 emissions in the WAM scenario below their emission level in 2024. Iceland projects an increase of EU ETS1 emissions under both scenarios. In three Member States (Czechia, Germany, and Romania) EU ETS1 emissions in the WAM scenario are higher than in the WEM scenario. This effect can be explained by a trend for increased electrification in

the transport and buildings sector. If the higher demand for electricity is not accompanied with a respective increase of renewable power supply, emissions from fossil-fueled power supply increase.

Figure 3-3 shows the historic development until 2024 as well as the projected development after 2030 in the WAM scenario. Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Norway and Sweden did not submit projections for a WAM scenario. For Iceland and Malta, no difference between the WEM and WAM scenario has been projected for EU ETS1 emissions, but additional measures show effects on emission covered under the Effort Sharing Regulation. For these countries, the result of scenarios with existing measures is shown. In the WAM scenario, stationary EU ETS1 emissions are projected to fall by 81.1 % from 2005¹³ until 2050.

Figure 3-3 Historic and projected changes with additional measures (WAM) until 2050 in stationary ETS1 emissions relative to 2005 emission levels

Note: In this figure historic EU ETS1 emissions 2024 are used, so that the total reduction until 2050 displayed by country informs about the development compared to historic EU ETS1 emissions 2024.

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025

For countries with reductions across all three periods (2005-2024, 2024-2030 and 2030-2050), these can be added so that the aggregated bar in Figure 3-3 shows the total stationary EU ETS1 reduction in 2050 compared to 2005 for the WAM scenario. Three countries shown on the right-hand side project increases in EU ETS1 stationary emissions after 2024. In Denmark emissions are even projected to increase after 2030.

The level of EU ETS1 emissions in Iceland in 2050 is projected to be higher than 2005 levels (0.08 Mt CO₂-eq). In previous projections, Finland showed negative EU ETS1 emissions in 2050 through the use of

¹³ Emissions from 2005 to 2013 were adjusted to reflect the current scope of the EU ETS1. This alignment enables a consistent comparison over time by accounting for changes in scope, following the methodology established by Graichen et al. (2017).

BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage) in its WEM scenario. With this year’s projections, only Czechia projects negative emissions in the long term. Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, and Slovenia project emission reductions of more than 90% compared to 2005 until 2050.

Figure 3-4 displays absolute stationary emissions projected for 2030 and 2050 (with additional measures) in those ten countries with the highest emissions in 2030, compared to all other countries. Nearly all countries with highest absolute emissions show emission reductions in this timeframe, only Romania projects increasing emissions between 2030 and 2050. The biggest emission reduction in absolute terms between 2030 and 2050 is projected to take place in Germany, closely followed by Poland. Compared to last year’s projections, EU ETS1 emissions submitted by Poland are considerably lower in both scenarios, hence Germany is now projected to be the largest emitter of EU ETS1 emissions in 2030 and 2050.

Figure 3-4 Absolute projected stationary EU ETS1 emissions in the years 2030 and 2050 in the WAM scenario

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025

3.1.4 Emission trends by sector

Figure 3-5 displays aggregated historic and projected stationary EU ETS1 emissions by sector. Historically, reductions mainly took place in the energy industries sector and this trend is projected to continue. After 2030, the pace of emission reductions in this sector slows down and nearly stabilises after 2040 under the scenario with existing measures.

EU ETS1 emissions from industrial processes are projected to show a very small downward trend until 2030 and close to no change afterwards. Emissions from manufacturing and construction installations, shown as ‘other industries’, are projected to decrease with a similar reduction rate as emissions from industrial processes until 2050.

Figure 3-5 EU ETS1 historic and projected emissions between 2005 and 2050 for the EU-27

Notes: Solid lines represent historical greenhouse gas emissions up to 2022. Dashed lines represent projections under the 'with existing measures' WEM scenario. Dotted lines represent projections under the 'with additional measures' (WAM) scenario. This figure refers to EU ETS1 emissions of the EU-27 only. Historic emissions by sector were estimated based on the attribution of GHG emissions, reported by source categories in GHG inventories. 'Energy industries' cover CRF categories 1A1, 1B2 and 1C. 'Other industries' are related to CRF category 1A2 while 'industrial processes' are related to CRF category 2. The estimate of the share of ETS1 emissions in these sectors is based on relevant assumptions in national GHG projections.

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2024

3.2 Aviation

3.2.1 Overview

According to the latest submissions, projected emissions from aviation activities are considerably lower than in previous submissions. The absolute level of emissions in 2050 has decreased by about 20 Mt CO₂, mainly because of lower projections from Germany. In addition, different to last year, aviation emissions are now projected to decrease slowly from 2030 onwards (Figure 3-6). However, this reduction is still not in line with the overall EU-wide target to achieve climate neutrality in 2050, nor with the ReFuelEU Aviation Regulation, which is expected to reduce CO₂ emissions from air transport by around two-thirds by 2050 compared to a 'no action' scenario (EC 2023). The new rules under this regulation require fuel suppliers to blend sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) with kerosene in increasing amounts from 2025 onwards.

3.2.2 Emission trends

By 2019, historical EU ETS aviation emissions were significantly higher than projections because GHG projections no longer include emissions of the United Kingdom. In 2020, emissions (still including the United Kingdom) dropped significantly due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting decrease in air traffic.

Projections for aviation emissions by EEA countries do not differentiate between those covered by the EU ETS1 and those outside of the system. That is why the EU ETS aviation emissions depicted in Figure 3-6 are calculated by applying EU ETS1 shares to projected domestic and international aviation emissions. For domestic aviation emissions, a full inclusion into the EU ETS1 is assumed, while for international aviation, a share based on historic data is estimated and applied. With the inclusion of flights from outermost regions to other EEA countries from 2024 onwards, emissions covered under the EU ETS1 increased. This is why the historic EU ETS1 share of 32 % has increased to 37 % from 2024 onwards.

At the end of 2027, the European Commission is set to publish a proposal for if and how non-CO₂ effects of aviation shall be included under the EU ETS1 (Article 14 (EU) 2023/959). A respective increase of the EU ETS1 share has not been considered here.

Figure 3-6 EU ETS1 emissions for aviation between 2012 and 2050

Notes: The sharp drop in aviation emissions from 2012 to 2013 reflects a change in the scope of aviation activities covered by the EU ETS1. ETS aviation emissions can't be separated by countries, this is why for CO₂ projections the figure refers to all countries covered by the EU ETS1 in respective years. GHG projections no longer include the United Kingdom, which results in a systematic different level of ETS aviation emissions from 2021 on compared to emissions before 2020.

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025

3.3 Maritime Transport

3.3.1 Overview

Maritime transport emissions have been included under the EU ETS1 since 2024 and this year's report is the first to include projections of this sector within the annual report series. The calculated cap on maritime emissions gives an indication of the targeted reduction of emissions in this sector: following this calculated cap, emissions should decrease by 50.8 % compared to 2005 emissions until 2030.

Similarly to aviation, maritime transport emissions are expected to increase until 2050 based on the WEM and WAM projections of EU Member States (see Figure 3-7 below). This is in contrast to projections published in the Commission's Impact Assessment related to the EU ETS1 extension to maritime transport. The Impact Assessment projects emissions to decline by 92 % by 2050 compared to the reference scenario (absolute maritime transport emissions of 161 Mt CO₂ in 2050) (EC 2024).

3.3.2 Emission trend

Since 2007, emissions from international EU-related maritime transport have generally decreased. There was a steep increase of emissions between 1990 and 2007 with a drop afterwards due to the global economic crisis (IMO 2020; EC 2025a). The drop in emissions in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic was not as steep as for aviation, given that mainly maritime passenger transport was impacted.

In 2024, 66 % of the EU-wide maritime emissions were covered by the EU ETS1.

Figure 3-7 EU ETS1 shipping emissions between 2005 and 2050

Note: Historic and projected emissions are calculated with the estimate of a constant share of EU ETS1 emissions on international navigation emissions as reported in GHG inventory and national projections.

The EU ETS1 stationary cap was adjusted in 2024 to account for inclusion of the maritime sector. The target shown in this figure has been calculated from the aggregated EU ETS1 cap in 2024, which is a cap together for stationary and maritime emissions.

Sources: EEA (2025b), projections of EU Member States compiled by the European Topic Centre for Climate Change Mitigation (ETC/CM) as of September 2025

Emission projections under both existing and additional measures suggest that EU ETS1 maritime emissions in 2025 will be around 5 Mt CO₂-eq higher than the 2024 inventory value. Member States do not report maritime EU ETS1 projections directly, instead they provide projections for total domestic and international navigation. Maritime EU ETS1 projections were therefore derived by applying the 2024 share of EU ETS1 maritime emissions to the reported international navigation projections. The accuracy of these projections is expected to improve as more historical data becomes available.

The calculated target shown in Figure 3-7 for the maritime sector under the EU ETS1 is around 15 Mt CO₂-eq lower than 2024 emissions. This target was derived from the combined EU ETS1 cap, which covers both emissions from stationary installations and the maritime sector.¹⁴ If maritime emissions exceed this estimated target, additional emission reductions in other EU ETS1 sectors will be required to ensure total emissions remain within the combined cap.

From 2026 onwards, methane and nitrous oxide emissions from maritime transport will also be covered by the EU ETS1. Offshore ships will be covered as an additional ship type from 2027 onwards. A decision regarding the inclusion of smaller ships below 5,000 GT from 2027 onwards is expected in 2026 based on

¹⁴ The calculated target was derived from the cap increase of the EU ETS1 when in 2024 its scope was extended to include the maritime sector.

a review of the maritime ETS. These planned and pending extensions will increase the share of emissions covered by the EU ETS1 before 2030.

Several exemptions where shipping companies do not have to surrender allowances for their emissions will end after 2030, such as voyages to/from outermost regions and to/from small islands. The exemptions likely represent a small share of EU-related shipping emissions but will increase the share of covered emissions and demand for allowances after 2030.

Both these changes to the scope and covered emissions before and after 2030 were not considered in the projections shown in Figure 3-7 above.

At global level, negotiations at the International Maritime Organization (IMO) progressed in early 2025 with a draft agreement on an IMO Net-Zero Framework (NZF) containing a new fuel standard with an economic element (IMO 2025). However, the extraordinary meeting at IMO in October 2025 did not result in an adoption of the NZF and the decision was postponed by one year. The European Commission is tasked with submitting a report to examining this potential new IMO measure within 18 months of the adoption of such a measure regarding its ambition and coherence with the EU ETS1. If appropriate, the Commission may propose amendments to the Emissions Trading Directive in that regard.

4 Focus Topic: EU ETS2

Key messages:

- **Start of the EU ETS2 originally planned for 2027 but likely moved to 2028, start of the Social Climate Fund in 2026:** The EU ETS2 will cover CO₂ emissions from the combustion of fuels in road transport and buildings, as well as industry not currently covered by EU ETS1. A recent Council decision and European Parliamentary vote make it likely that the start will be postponed to 2028. In 2026, the Social Climate Fund will start to operate, with the goal of supporting vulnerable groups in reducing their fossil fuel consumption through targeted investments and programmes.
- **Importance of road transport in the EU ETS2:** Road transport contributes the majority of emissions in EU ETS2 sectors across the system. It will be crucial to reduce these emissions to align with the ambitious climate goals of the EU and ensure that the EU ETS2 allowance price remains at sustainable levels.
- **Importance of buildings sector depends on fuel mix used for heating energy:** Countries where the heating system is based on district heating (mostly covered by EU ETS1) and electricity or renewables, have low EU ETS2 emissions in the buildings sector. Countries where the heating system is based on individual fossil-fueled boilers have high EU ETS2 emission shares in the buildings sector.
- **Modest historical progress in EU ETS2 sectors:** Emissions within EU ETS2 sectors have been declining at a slower rate than those in EU ETS1 sectors. Within the EEA, emissions in EU ETS2 sectors declined by 6.7 % between 2015 and 2023, whereas EU ETS1 emissions declined by 32.7 % over the same period.
- **Steady decrease of projected EU ETS2 emissions until 2050 with a large impact of additional measures:** Projected EU ETS2 emissions decrease steadily until 2050. Projections between the WEM and WAM scenarios diverge strongly, indicating an important contribution of planned policies and measures on the emissions reductions in EU ETS2 sectors.

Overview

The EU ETS2 covers CO₂ emissions from combustion of fossil fuels in the road transport and the buildings sector, as well as CO₂ emissions from the combustion of these fuels in smaller industrial installations that are currently not covered under the EU ETS1. The system was introduced as part of the Fit for 55 package to accelerate emission reductions in those sectors where emissions have not declined in line with the ambitious climate targets of the EU. The EU ETS2 scope applies to 40 % of the EU's 2024 GHG emissions. It is set out to become a core element of European climate policy, with an aim to reduce the covered emissions by 42 % in 2030 compared to 2005 levels (EC n.d.).

The EU ETS2 entered into a transitional period in 2024 with regulated entities already having to monitor and report their emissions. The system was to become fully operational in 2027 but will now likely be postponed to 2028¹⁵. From then onwards, regulated entities will have to surrender emission allowances corresponding to their annual emissions. The EU ETS2 functions in the same way as the EU ETS1, operating as a cap-and-trade system. Regulated entities are subject to an annually declining emissions cap and need to surrender sufficient allowances to cover their emissions in each year. The ETS2 allowances are tradable

¹⁵ Member States have proposed to delay the start of the EU ETS2 by one year. The proposal for the new start of the system is supported by the European Parliament but not yet enshrined in law.

and can be purchased at auctions, on the market or via direct trades with other market participants. There will be no free allocation in the EU ETS2, all allowances will be distributed via auctions.

Contrary to the EU ETS1 the system operates as an upstream system. Fuel suppliers will be charged with the EU ETS2 costs, that they will then pass on to the consumers of the covered fuels. Thus, EU ETS2 prices will impact consumer prices and make the purchase of the covered fossil fuels more costly compared to climate-friendly alternatives. This is the price signal that should induce the reduction of fossil fuel use and thus CO₂ emissions in the covered sectors.

Recognising that higher prices for fossil fuels that are used to heat homes, fuel mobility, and power businesses can pose a burden to vulnerable groups, the EU is introducing a Social Climate Fund (SCF) along with the EU ETS2. The SCF is fed by a share of EU ETS2 auctioning revenues and the funds are distributed to Member States based on a mechanism that considers CO₂ emission levels in the covered sectors and the likely size of the groups of vulnerable households, transport users and micro-enterprises in each country. Member States have to establish Social Climate Plans (SCPs) detailing how they will spend the available funds. There is a clear focus on supporting vulnerable groups via investments in energy efficiency improvements of their home or business, renewable heating and climate-friendly mobility, as the transition away from fossil fuels is a long-term insurance against rising fossil fuel costs and CO₂ prices. As a transitional measure, Member States can also provide direct income support to the identified vulnerable group (EC n.d.).

To prevent excessive price increases and high price volatility in the EU ETS2, the system includes several price stability mechanisms, including the Market Stability Reserve 2 (MSR 2) and a soft price ceiling of 45 EUR/tCO₂. (EC n.d.). In October 2025, the European Commission announced to further strengthen these mechanisms (DG CLIMA 2025a).

Figure 4-1 shows the sectoral share of emissions in ETS2 sectors by country in 2023. Across all EEA countries, road transport emissions contributed 60.8 % of the total emissions in EU ETS2 sectors. Emissions from the buildings and energy and industry sector made up 28.3 % and 10.9 %, respectively.

Figure 4-1 EU ETS2 emission scope by sector and Member State in 2023

Note: The EU ETS2 emission scope was calculated backwards based on the sectors the system will cover.

Source: Author's compilation based on data from EEA (2025a; 2025b).

Road transport is responsible for the majority of emissions in EU ETS2 sectors in all EEA countries, with the exception of Liechtenstein. The highest road transport emission shares are observed in Iceland, Sweden, and Bulgaria, where road transport emissions contribute between 89.8 % and 84.7 % to the total national emissions in EU ETS2 sectors. Germany and Liechtenstein are the two EEA countries with the lowest share of road transport emissions in total emissions from EU ETS2 sectors, as a large part of their EU ETS2 emissions originate in the buildings sector. The buildings sector is typically the second biggest emitting sector amongst the three EU ETS2 sectors. The split between sectors depends on the fuel mix in those sectors in the individual countries. Countries where a lot of fossil fuels are burnt in individual boilers used for heating, have a higher share of buildings sectors emissions, whereas countries where homes are heated using renewables, electricity or district heating have a lower share of buildings sector emissions in overall emissions from EU ETS2 sectors. Emissions from the combustion of covered fuels in the energy and industry sectors not covered by the EU ETS1 represent around 10 % of total EU ETS2 emissions in most countries with some exceptions, like Romania and Czechia where energy and industry emissions represent 23.2 % and 19.1 % of ETS2 emissions, respectively.

While Figure 4-1 shows that the three EU ETS2 sectors have a different importance across EEA countries, road transport will play an important role in the EU ETS2 across all EEA countries. The fuel mix in the heating sector and technologies used in the energy and industry sector will determine the specific mitigation strategies for the other EU ETS2 emissions in each country.

4.1 Emission trends

Figure 4-2 shows the change in GHG emissions for stationary EU ETS1 emissions, emissions in EU ETS2 sectors, and total GHG emissions between 2015 and 2023 for EEA countries. In the EEA both emissions in the EU ETS1 and in EU ETS2 sectors decreased. EU ETS1 emissions fell by 32.7 % between 2015 and 2023 while emissions in EU ETS2 sectors declined by 6.7 %. Total gross GHG emission reductions (excluding LULUCF) across the EEA amount to 18.5 % between 2015 and 2023.

Figure 4-2 Evolution of EU ETS and total GHG emissions by Member State, 2015-2023

Note: The EU ETS2 emission scope was calculated backwards based on the sectors the system will cover. Liechtenstein is excluded from the calculations due to a lack of data. The left axis shows the relative change in EU ETS emissions and the right axis shows the relative change in total gross GHG emissions excluding LULUCF emissions.

Source: Author's compilation based on data from EEA (2025a; 2025b).

In general, emission reductions in EU ETS1 sectors were larger than in the EU ETS2 sectors for all countries except for Sweden. 11 out of 29 countries even recorded an increase in emissions in the EU ETS2 sectors between 2015 and 2023. This was mainly driven by an increase in road transport emissions, with Romania's road transport emissions rising by 42.4 % and Poland's by 45.0 % over eight years.

Total GHG emissions decreased in all EEA countries since 2015 apart from Croatia, Cyprus, and Malta, where emissions increased by between 4.6 % and 2.1 %. This increase was mainly driven by the increase in emissions in EU ETS2 sectors. The largest total emissions reductions were recorded in Estonia with a 39.4 % reduction and in the Netherlands and Germany with a 26.7 % and 25.5 % reduction, respectively.

Figure 4-3 shows historic and projected emissions in the EU ETS1 and the scope of the EU ETS2 from 2005 to 2050. Emissions in the EU ETS1 have more than halved from around 2.1 Gt CO₂ in 2005 to just above 1 Gt in 2023. In contrast emissions in EU ETS2 sectors have only decreased by 18.1 % over the same time period.

Figure 4-3 Historic and projected emissions of ETS1 and ETS2

Note: EU ETS1 numbers are excluding the UK. ETS1 emissions from 2005 to 2013 are adjusted to reflect the current scope of the EU ETS1. This alignment enables a consistent comparison over time by accounting for changes in scope, following the methodology established by Graichen et al. (2017). EU ETS2 emission scope was calculated backwards based on the sectors the system will cover. Dotted lines show the emission projections under a scenario with existing measures (WEM) and with additional measures (WAM).

Source: Author's compilation based on data from EEA (2025a; 2025b).

Estimates for historic emissions in EU ETS2 sectors show small fluctuations over the years, which reflect the general economic development of the Eurozone, e.g., the recession in 2008 or the sharp decline in economic activity in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a sharp decrease in emissions from one year to the next, especially in road transport related emissions. After these economic shocks, emissions in EU ETS2 sectors quickly rebound to pre-crisis levels. Starting in 2021, emissions in EU ETS2 sectors fell by around 80 Mt over two consecutive years.

EEA countries' project that emissions in both the EU ETS1 and EU ETS2 sectors fall steadily until 2050 (for details regarding the EU ETS1 projections see section 3). Emission projections for EU ETS2 sectors in the scenario reflecting current policies and the scenario including additional policy measures diverge substantially. While EU ETS1 emission projections show a maximum difference of 118.4 Mt CO₂-eq between both scenarios in 2050, the EU ETS2 projections differ by 270.9 Mt CO₂ in 2050. Under the more ambitious scenario EU ETS2 emissions are projected to fall to 202.0 Mt CO₂ by 2050, whereas under current policies, emissions are only expected to decline to 472.8 Mt CO₂.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEA	European Economic Area
AFIR	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Development
CRF	Common Reporting Framework
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEX	European Energy Exchange
EMSA	European Maritime Safety Agency
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
ETC CM	European Topic Centre on Climate Change Mitigation
EU ETS	EU Emissions Trading Scheme
EUA	EU Allowances
EUA	EU Aviation Allowances
EUTL	EU Transaction Log
GT	Gross Tonnage
IMO	International Maritime Organization
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
MSR	Market Stability Reserve
NER	New Entrants Reserve
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuels
TNAC	Total Number of Allowances in Circulation
WAM	With Additional Measures
WEM	With Existing Measures

References

Bonnet, A. (2025): Why Linking EU and UK Emissions Trading Systems Is a Win–Win for the Economy and the Environment, International Institute for Sustainable Development. Online available at <https://www.iisd.org/articles/insight/eu-uk-deal-agreement-emissions>, last updated on 22 May 2025, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

CBAM Regulation (2023): European Parliament; Council of the European Union. Regulation (EU) 2023/956 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 establishing a carbon border adjustment mechanism, CBAM Regulation. In: Official Journal of the European Union (O.J.) (L 130/52). Online available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023R0956>, last accessed on 19 Nov 2024.

DG CLIMA - Directorate-General for Climate Action (2025a): Ensuring a stable start for Europe’s new carbon market for buildings and road transport. News Article, European Commission. Online available at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-other-reads/news/ensuring-stable-start-europes-new-carbon-market-buildings-and-road-transport-2025-10-21_en, last updated on 21 Oct 2025, last accessed on 7 Nov 2025.

DG CLIMA - European Commission (2025b): Adoption of EU rules on the ETS support system to accelerate the use of sustainable aviation fuels, European Commission. Online available at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news/adoption-eu-rules-ets-support-system-accelerate-use-sustainable-aviation-fuels-2025-02-06_en, last updated on 6 Feb 2025, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

DG CLIMA - European Commission (2025c): Union Registry – Operators Daily [CSV-File], Data Download, European Commission. Online available at <https://union-registry-data.ec.europa.eu/report/welcome>, last updated on 1 Jul 2025.

DG CLIMA - European Commission (2025d): Union Registry - Operators Yearly Activity Daily [CSV-File], Data Download, European Commission. Online available at <https://union-registry-data.ec.europa.eu/report/welcome>, last updated on 1 Jul 2025.

Directive (EU) 2023/959 (2024): European Parliament; European Council. Directive (EU) 2023/959 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 amending Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and Decision (EU) 2015/1814 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading system (Text with EEA relevance), Directive (EU) 2023/959. Online available at <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/959/oj>, last accessed on 13 Jun 2024.

EC - European Commission (2023): European Green Deal: new law agreed to cut aviation emissions by promoting

sustainable aviation fuels. European Commission (ed.). Brüssel.

EC - European Commission (2024): Commission staff working document impact assessment report part 1 accompanying the document communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the committee of the regions securing our future Europe’s 2040 climate target and path to climate neutrality by 2050 building a sustainable, just and prosperous society, European Commission. Online available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex:52024SC0063>, last accessed on 20 Apr 2025.

EC - European Commission (2025a): 2024 Report from the European Commission on CO2 Emissions from Maritime Transport, SWD(2025) 38 final. Online available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/625b4330-ea86-11ef-b5e9-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

EC - European Commission (2025b): Communication from the Commission - Publication of the total number of allowances in circulation in 2024 for the purposes of the Market Stability Reserve under the EU Emissions Trading System. Online available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52025XC03180>, last accessed on 18 Aug 2025.

EC - European Commission (ed.) (2021): Update of benchmark values for the years 2021-2025 of phase 4 of the EU ETS, Benchmark curves and key parameters. Online available at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-10/policy_ets_allowances_bm_curve_factsheets_en.pdf, last accessed on 25 Jun 2021.

EC - European Commission (ed.) (n.d.): ETS2: buildings, road transport and additional sectors. Online available at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/ets2-buildings-road-transport-and-additional-sectors_en, last accessed on 1 Jul 2025.

EC - European Commission (n.d.): Social Climate Fund, European Commission. Online available at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/carbon-markets/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/social-climate-fund_en, last accessed on 20 Sep 2025.

EEA - European Environment Agency (2019): Trends and projections in the EU ETS in 2019. Online available at https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cme/products/etc-cme-reports/etc-cme-report-3-2019-trends-and-projections-in-the-eu-ets-in-2019/@@download/file/ETC_CME_Technical_Report_2019_3%20final.pdf, last accessed on 30 Dec 2019.

EEA - European Environment Agency (2025a): EEA greenhouse gases — data viewer, European Environment Agency. Online available at

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/greenhouse-gases-viewer-data-viewers>, last accessed on 17 Sep 2025.

EEA - European Environment Agency (2025b): EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) data viewer, European Environment Agency. Online available at <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/emissions-trading-viewer-1-dashboards?activeTab=265e2bee-7de3-46e8-b6ee-76005f3f434f>, last updated on 30 Aug 2025.

EEX - European Energy Exchange (2025): EUA Primary Market Auction Report, European Energy Exchange. Online available at <https://www.eex.com/de/marktdaten/umweltprodukte/ee-x-eua-primary-auction-spot-download>, last accessed on 18 Aug 2025.

EMSA - European Maritime Safety Agency (2024): THETIS-MRV, CO₂-Emission Report, European Maritime Safety Agency. Online available at <https://mrv.emsa.europa.eu/#public/emission-report>, last accessed on 14 Oct 2024.

ENTSO-E (2025): Actual Generation per Generation Unit, TP_export, ENTSO-E, last updated on 12.2024.

EU (2020): Notice on the Union-wide quantity of allowances for 2021 and the Market Stability Reserve under the EU Emissions Trading System (2020/C 428 I/01). Source of information: Official Journal of the European Union, Volume 63, 11 December 2020. Online available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:2020:428I:FULL&from=EN>, last accessed on 6 Apr 2021.

Eurostat (2025): Net electricity generation by type of fuel, monthly data; NRG_CB_PEM, Eurostat. Online available at https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/NRG_CB_PEM_custom_7296483/default/table, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

FOEN - Federal Office for the Environment (2025): Swiss Emissions Trading Registry, Federal Office for the Environment. Online available at <https://www.emissionsregistry.admin.ch/crweb/public/reporting/allocation/list.action?token=MV3XU25XCZPKY2ZWC MHJ7VQ83L63CZAY>, last updated on 19 Aug 2025.

Graichen, V. and Wissner, N. (2023): Aviation in the EU ETS and CORSIA in the 'Fit for 55' package, The EU agreement of June 2023. Oeko-Institut. Umweltbundesamt (ed.). Online available at https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/11850/publikationen/09_2023_factsheet_aviation_in_the_eu_ets_and_corsia.pdf, last accessed on 10 Nov 2023.

Graichen, V.; Cludius, J.; Gores, S. (2017): Estimate of 2005 - 2012 emissions for stationary installations to reflect the current scope (2013 - 2020) of the EU ETS, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2017/11. European Environment Agency. Online available at

http://acm.eionet.europa.eu/reports/ETCACM_TP_2017_11_estimates_reflect_current_ETS_scope, last accessed on 22 Jan 2018.

Hermann, H.; Gores, S.; Nissen, C. (2021): Matching of power plants by fuel, For the EEA EU ETS dataviewer (ETC/CME Eionet Report, 10/2021). ETC/CME. ETC/CME (ed.). Online available at <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cme/products/etc-cme-reports/etc-cme-report-10-2021-matching-of-power-plants-by-fuel>, last accessed on 20 Sep 2022.

ICAP - International Carbon Action Partnership (2025a): EU and UK commit to linking emissions trading systems in landmark cooperation agreement, International Carbon Action Partnership. Online available at <https://icapcarbonaction.com/en/news/eu-and-uk-commit-linking-emissions-trading-systems-landmark-cooperation-agreement>, last updated on 22 May 2025, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

ICAP - International Carbon Action Partnership (2025b): UK Emissions Trading Scheme, International Carbon Action Partnership. Online available at <https://icapcarbonaction.com/en/ets/uk-emissions-trading-scheme>, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

ICE - Intercontinental Exchange (2021): Auctions - EUA UK, Market Data, Intercontinental Exchange. Online available at <https://www.theice.com/marketdata/reports/148>, last accessed on 14 Jul 2021.

IMO - International Maritime Organization (2020): Fourth IMO GHG Study 2020, Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships (MEPC 75/7/15). London. Online available at <https://www.imo.org/en/ourwork/Environment/Pages/Fourth-IMO-Greenhouse-Gas-Study-2020.aspx>, last accessed on 24 Oct 2020.

IMO (2025): Draft revised MARPOL Annex VI, Circular Letter No. 5005. Online available at <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Documents/Circular%20Letter%20No.5005%20-%20Draft%20Revised%20Marpol%20Annex%20Vi%2028Scretariat%29.pdf>, last accessed on 23 Sep 2025.

Nissen, C.; Cludius, J.; Gores, S.; Hermann, H.; Wissner, N. (2024): Trends and projections in the EU ETS in 2024, The EU Emissions Trading System in numbers (ETC-CM Report, 2024/09). European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation. European Environment Agency (ed.). Online available at <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cm/products/etc-cm-report-2024-09>, last accessed on 2 May 2025.

Nissen, C.; Gores, S.; Healy, S.; Hermann, H. (2023): Trends and projections in the EU ETS in 2023, The EU Emissions Trading System in numbers (ETC-CM Report, 2023/07). European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation. European Environment Agency (ed.). Online available at <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cm/products/etc-cm-report-2023-07->

1/@@download/file/ETC_CM_ETS%20Report_2023_07_2.pdf, last accessed on 17 Sep 2024.

Twidale, S. and Abnett, K. (2025): Britain facing race to avoid \$1 billion in EU carbon tax costs. Reuters (ed.). Online available at <https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/climate-energy/britain-facing-race-avoid-1-billion-eu-carbon-tax-costs-2025-06-02/>, last updated on 3 Jun 2025, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

UK Government (2025): Methodology note: assessing the preliminary economic impacts of linking the UK-EU Emission Trading Schemes, UK Government. Online available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/methodology-note-preliminary-economic-impacts-of-linking-the-uk-eu-emission-trading-schemes/methodology-note-assessing-the-preliminary-economic-impacts-of-linking-the-uk-eu-emission-trading-schemes>, last updated on 19 May 2025, last accessed on 19 Aug 2025.

Wissner, N. and Cames, M. (2023): Extension of the EU ETS to maritime transport, Key aspects of the revision of the ETS directive. Oeko-Institut. Umweltbundesamt (ed.). Online available at https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/11850/publikationen/factsheet_seeverkehr_en.pdf, last accessed on 23 Jul 2025.

Annex 1

Table A-12 Activities and sectors covered by the EU ETS1 grouped

Activities	Sectors	
20 Combustion of fuels	Combustion	Stationary Installations
21 Refining of mineral oil	Refineries	
22 Production of coke	Iron and steel, coke, metal ore	
23 Metal ore roasting or sintering		
24 Production of pig iron or steel		
25 Production or processing of ferrous metals		
26 Production of primary aluminium	Other metals (incl. aluminium)	
27 Production of secondary aluminium		
28 Production or processing of non-ferrous metals		
29 Production of cement clinker	Cement and lime	
30 Production of lime, or calcination of dolomite/magnesite		
31 Manufacture of glass	Other non-metallic minerals	
32 Manufacture of ceramics		
33 Manufacture of mineral wool		
34 Production or processing of gypsum or plasterboard		
35 Production of pulp	Pulp and paper	
36 Production of paper or cardboard		
37 Production of carbon black	Chemicals	
38 Production of nitric acid		
39 Production of adipic acid		
40 Production of glyoxal and glyoxylic acid		
41 Production of ammonia		
42 Production of bulk chemicals		
43 Production of hydrogen and synthesis gas		
44 Production of soda ash and sodium bicarbonate		
45 Capture of greenhouse gases under Directive 2009/31/EC	Other	
99 Other activity opted-in under Art. 24		
10 Aviation	Aviation	Transport under the EU ETS1
50 Maritime Transport	Maritime	

European Topic Centre on
Climate change mitigation

<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cm>

The European Topic Centre on Climate change mitigation (ETC-CM) is a consortium of European institutes under contract of the European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency
European Topic Centre
Climate change mitigation

